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The journal's structure covers all aspects of the fields approached, the focus being on original and current researches with applications in agriculture, food industry and rural tourism. Collaborators may feel free to undertake biological and technical aspects as well as aspects with social, cultural and environmental impact. Information of general interest is also welcome for the agriecology-food-tourism axis

Prof. Romulus Gruia Ph. D.

The Journal of EcoAgroTurism aims at approaching analyses, methodologies, options and references within the journal's framework.

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Since 1980, the United Nations World Tourism Organization (WTO) has been celebrating World Tourism Day, which was set for September 27. This date was chosen because on that day in 1970 the UNWTO Statutes were adopted. The adoption of these Statutes is considered an important stage in global tourism.

As an event prior to this day, on September 25 is celebrated the *World Agri Tourism Day* which is why we announce this event and for the field of agrotourism, so important in the economic profile of Romania, announcement supported by our magazine "Journal of EcoAgriTourism".

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SUMMARY

Editorial : WORLD AGRI TOURISM DAY - GRUIA Romulus	
5	<i>IDENTIFICATION AND PRESERVATION OF LEISHMANICIDAL PLANTS USED IN SETIF STEPPE (ALGERIA)</i> <i>S.CHERMAT, L.OUKSEL</i>
14	<i>A 2019 STUDY ON DEOXYNIVALENOL AND ZEARALENONE LEVELS IN ROMANIAN BARLEY (HORDEUM VULGARE L.) SAMPLES</i> <i>I. SMEU, H. CASIAN</i>
21	<i>DESIGN PRINCIPLES FOR ASSURING FOOD SAFETY IN ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN DAIRY FARMS</i> <i>L. GACEU</i>
26	<i>NEW HORIZONS IN THE FOOD ACT: TISSUE ENGINEERING AND PRODUCTION OF BIOCELLULAR FOOD</i> <i>R. GRUIA</i>
35	<i>IMPORTANCE OF WOOD BIOMASS IN ROMANIA</i> <i>GH.C. SPIRCHEZ, A. LUNGULEASA, L. GACEU</i>
39	<i>NATURAL HONEY MARKET: EU28 AND BRICS COMPETITIVENESS EVIDENCES REGARDING MOUNTAIN NATURAL HONEY</i> <i>B. COVACI</i>
45	<i>DEMARCATIION AND PROTECTION OF <i>Pistacia atlantica</i> Desf. IN SETIFIAN STEPPE (NORTH- EAST OF ALGERIA)</i> <i>L. S.CHERMAT, R.BOUNAR</i>
51	<i>FOOD SAFETY IN PASTEURIZATION OF LIQUID FOOD - BASIC ELEMENTS FOR MOUNTAIN FARMERS</i> <i>L. GACEU</i>

IDENTIFICATION AND PRESERVATION OF LEISHMANICIDAL PLANTS USED IN SETIF STEPPE (ALGERIA)

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Abstract: Center of cutaneous leishmaniasis, the Setif steppes is currently experiencing a significant upsurge in this endemic and parasitic disease. To treat themselves the majority of the rural population has resorted mainly to toxic plants known for their magical and healing properties. The present study focused on the plant species potentially used in the treatment of these diseases. The floristic inventory identified six vascular species, including *Peganum harmala* L., *Carlina gummifera* (L.) Less., *Deverra scoparia* Coss. and two cryptogam species of scaly lichens (*Lecanora esculenta* Evernsmann and *Rhizoplaca melanophthalma* (DC.) Leuckert). These taxes constitute the most natural and effective antileishmanian remedy in the rural community. For the therapeutic route, our follow-up surveys are based on participatory observation, the knowledge held by the healers, the attitude of the users, the practices and the treatment time. These have enabled us to refine our knowledge and perception of the application of traditional herbal treatment, which is of great importance at the regional level where the nomadic and sedentary populations still have knowledge of leishmanicide species. It turns out that more in-depth scientific research will have to develop this empirical knowledge for a better management and preservation of this floristic heritage by fighting against this epidemiology which prevails in Algeria.

Keywords: Cutaneous leishmaniasis, Plants, Treatment and perception, Preservation, Steppe.

1. Introduction

Declared as the first country affected by leishmaniasis in the Mghreb, Algeria is considered as an area with old and new endemic foci of this infectious disease. Leishmaniasis is a globally expanding disease, it is caused by flagellated protozoa that cause the different forms of leishmaniasis in humans [1]. These are emerging diseases and closely related to the state of the environment [2].

According to the World Health Organization (O.M.S., 2014), leishmaniasis is endemic in more than 80 countries around the world where 350 million people are at risk. These infections are experiencing a significant resurgence, justified by its annual incidence estimated at more than 1.3 million new cases per year. In North Africa, Algeria is among the countries most exposed to this disease in its various forms ranging from cutaneous form (LC) in the south to visceral form (LV) in the North. In Algeria, the study on cutaneous leishmaniasis is still very superficial and fragmentary indeed, most of the existing work concerns epidemiological studies of the

different forms of leishmaniasis and their emergence through ancient foci. Among the most recent works are : eco-epidemiological study of leishmaniasis in the Hodna basin[3]; characterization of the *Leishmania* strains responsible for cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Annaba[4], extension of *Leishmania major* to the north of Algeria [5]; inventory of cases of cutaneous leishmaniasis in Algiers[6]; cutaneous leishmaniasis caused by *Leishmania tropica* in Algeria[7].

The study on the recrudescence of cutaneous leishmaniasis in the wilaya of Tizi-Ouzou[8]. Concerning the old works in the same research axis on the problems of the cutaneous leishmaniasis epidemic in the M'sila and Ksar Chellala region [9], followed by the study by of *Leishmania infantum* and *Leishmania major* in Algeria [10]. Indeed, these epidemiological works were carried out to follow the evolution of leishmaniasis with the objective is the prevention and fight against the vectors responsible for the transmission of this disease.

Long confined to the historic focus of Biskra (southern Algeria) and known under the name of

the nail of Biskra or Hab-es-sana (button of one year), the LC is due to *Leishmania major*, this type of leishmaniasis prevails in the High Plains of Sétifiennes (HPS). And particularly in Ain Oulmen where it creates serious public health problems. No study has been carried out so far on the traditional treatment or Phyto-treatment of leishmaniasis practiced in Algeria.

Currently, one of the priorities in terms of the fight against LC by a so-called conventional medicine is to complete the epidemiological studies by the inventory of leishmanicidal plants and the monitoring of their application by an ethnobotanical study. Taking into account the lack of present study in Algeria, our investigations aim at the elaboration of a first list of antileishmanian and antiparasitic plants for the Sétifiennes steppes and for Algeria thus allowing their monitoring and biological integration in the development of pharmaceutical products.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Characteristics of the study area

The study area is located in the northeast of Algeria. Due to its overlapping geographic

location on the Tellian Atlas to the north and the Saharan influence of the Hodna Mountains to the south, it is representative of the semi-arid steppes, a floristic feature in the Setif High Plains.

Belonging to the Daira of Ain oulmen in the southwest of the wilaya of Sétif, it is defined by 6 hamlets (Douars) (fig.1): Douar Ouled Ahcene; Douar Chouaker; Douar Bouhrize; Douar Ouled Ammar; Douar Ouled Azzi and Hammam Ouled Yelles. From a Biogeographic point of view, it belongs to the North African steppe domain [11, 12, 13] to the high plateaux sector and the Constantin high plateaux sub-sector [14].

According to [15], the demarcated region is in a semi-arid bioclimate less than cool winter, with average precipitation estimated at 440.60 mm/year and thermal amplitudes varying between 1.94°C and 37.7°C with a relatively long dry season of 5 and a half months. Belonging to the floor of semi-arid Meso-Mediterranean vegetation, the flora of this ecosystem is remarkable with notably steppe chamaephyte formations very rich in medicinal species [16].

Fig. 1. Location of the site operated in the semi-arid steppe of Setif

2.2. The choice and description of the places surveyed

Our choice in this rural area stems on the one hand from the high use of medicinal plants and

the know-how held by sedentary and transhumant inhabitants and on the other hand, from the representativeness of several cases of people affected by cutaneous leishmaniasis and their

treatment with native plants whose origin is in the table 1.
Djebel Zdimm. The sectors investigated are given

Table 1. *Characteristics of the surveyed localities*

Locality	Type of locality	Geographic coordinates
Djebel Zdimm	- mountain range - 1212 of meters altitude	36° 1 '23.8 "North and 5° 10' 6" East
Douar Ouled Ammar	village	36° 0 '11.2 "North and 5° 12' 2.5" East
Douar Chouaker	hamlet	36° 0 '14.7 "North 5° 13' 9.2" East
Douar Bouhrize	hamlet	36° 0 '6.2 "North and 5° 14' 9.4" East
Douar Ouled Ahcene	hamlet	36° 1 '3.5 "North and 5° 14' 36.1" East
Douar Ouled Azzi	hamlet	36° 1 '28 "North and 5° 14' 58.8" East
Hammam-Ouled Yelles	hamlet	36° 3 '38.3 "North and 5° 12' 47" East
Nomadic settlements	- living in tents on the foothills of the northern slope of djebel Zdimm - lifestyle based on annual displacement.	no official geographic coding

*Douar = hamlet = grouping of dwellings.

2.3. Plant surveys and inventory

The present study was carried out from a series of ethnobotanical surveys using semi-structured interviews, a qualitative survey technique frequently used in research in the humanities and social sciences [17, 18].

The semi-structured interviewing is an informative data collection technique that contributes to the development of knowledge favoring qualitative and interpretative approaches to know-how [19, 20].

Indeed, this method allows us to collect and analyze several elements: the patient and the disease, the attitude of the interviewee, the selection of empirical material, the methodological procedures, inventory and valuation of the plant material used.

With a follow-up of 2 years (2017 - 2018) in the localities described and with our participating and curious observation on the behavior of the patients and the treating individuals, we were able to conduct our study in the triad (disease / treatment / plant) with 6 traditional healers (Marabout = Wizard), 18 local phytotherapist practitioners and 13 herbalists. For the confirmation of ethnobotanical data and using the vernacular names of plants, data collection was carried out with 100 informants from the local population.

For the comparative analysis and the fidelity of use of the spontaneous plants of Djebel Zdimm, we used Indices of conformity (Ic) which aims to assess the taxa potentially used against cutaneous leishmaniasis based on the consensus of the informants and the degree of cultural importance. A technique that takes into account the consensus of participants and can

thus be used to assess the cultural importance of plants is the proportion of informant agreement [21, 22, 23, 24]. For the comparison, we used data reported by the informants concerning the species, collected and used traditionally in the south of Setif.

The compliance index (Ic) is expressed by the ratio between The frequency of citation (FC) and the total number of people interviewed Nt, given by the following formula:

$$I_c = FC / N_t$$

For the determination of plant species, 8 collectors and suppliers of medicinal plants agreed to accompany us with them on Djebel Zdimm. Several study trips have been made to the Djebel Zdimm to inventory and identify with precision the species using the flora of North Africa Several [25, 14, 26].

For the attribution of biological types, recourse was made to the classification system of Raunkier [27].

After the precise identification of the plants, the specimens were deposited in the herbarium of the City and Territory Urban Project Laboratory of the University of Setif-1.

3. Results and discussion

After obtaining the favorable agreement thanks to the relationship of trust established with all the inhabitants of the region, we were able to carry out our monitoring with regard to three main order criteria:

- Medical (participatory observation of people affected by LC of each locality).

- Treatment and type of user (healer,
- The choice of plants (land covered for harvesting and determining plant species).

3.1. Selection of plants

Through ethnobotanical surveys of healers, Phytotherapists of users and the rural population of douars, we identified 6 vascular medicinal

phytotherapist and user).

plants and two other cryptogams distributed into 8 genera and 7 botanical families (table 2). These potentially used species are involved in the preparation of several locally prepared medicinal recipes.

Table 2. Distribution of species used by family and by morphological types in the semi-arid steppe of Setif

Botanical family	Number of species	Biological type
<i>Asteraceae</i>	1	Chamaephyte
<i>Zygophyllaceae</i>	1	Chamaephyte
<i>Apiaceae</i>	1	Chamaephyte
<i>Fabaceae</i>	1	phanerophyte
<i>Cupressaceae</i>	1	Phanerophyte
<i>Solanaceae</i>	1	Phanerophyte
<i>Lecanoraceae</i>	2	Scaly thallus,

The vascular plants are all perennials composed of 3 organic chamaephyte shrubs and organic phanerohytic trees representing similar rates of 37.5 % of the species. Cryptogams with a scaly thallus are represented by 2 taxa, i.e. 25 % of the Phytotreatment recommended in this region.

3.2. Parts of plants used and methods of preparation

For vascular species, the aerial organs (leaves, bark, stems and fruits) as well as the underground organs (roots) are the parts used. Seeds, leaves and roots predominate with a quotation frequency of 56.4 %. They are followed by a bark (stem and trunk) with 37 % and fresh fruit with 6.6 % of quotes.

Only for lichens all the thallus is used. The methods of preparation of the recipes recommended in the treatment of this disease are based on different formulations of the different parts of plants in the form of powders or pastes combined with camel fat and vegetable oils carefully selected by the healers.

Cade oil is the most used (locally extracted from *Juniperus oxycedrus* L.) representing 63.14

%, followed by olive oil (*Olea europea* L.) and pistachio oil (*Pistacia Atlantica*) with proportions similar to 18.43 % of the oils used.

Regarding the method of administration of the recipes, 100 % of the recipes is applied locally to the abscesses. The average duration of treatment varies from 15 to 20 days with one to three applications per day depending on the severity of the wound and the age of the patient.

3.3. Frequency of citation and confirmation index of taxa used

In total, we collected 402 citations from 137 informants. The most cited species are *Peganum harmala* L. with 91 citations or a percentage of 22.63 % of the plant material used, *Juniperus oxycedrus* L. with 87 citations (21.64 %) and *Carlina gummifera* (L.) Less, with 59 citations (14.67%) is shown in table 3.

The least cited are the cryptogamic species, *Lecanora esculenta* Evernsmann and *Rhizoplaca melanophthalma* (DC.) Leuckert, with a similar number of 17 citations representing 4.25 % for each species (fig. 2).

Fig.2. Frequency of use and confirmation indice of the species recommended against cutaneous leishmaniasis in the study area

Table 3. Number and frequency of citation of the species used against cutaneous leishmaniasis in the semi-arid Setifian steppe

Species	F.C	% C	Ic
<i>Peganum harmala</i> L.	91	22.63	0.66
<i>Juniperus oxycedrus</i> L.	87	21.64	0.63
<i>Carlina gummifera</i> (L.) Less.	59	14.67	0.43
<i>Deverra scoparia</i> Coss.	48	12.00	0.35
<i>Lycium arabicum</i> Boiss.	48	12.00	0.35
<i>Astragalus armatus</i> Willd. Ssp <i>tragacanthoides</i> (Desf.)Maire	35	8.71	0.25
<i>Lecanora esculenta</i> Evernsmann	17	4.23	0.12
<i>Rhizoplaca melanophthalma</i> (DC.) Leuckert	17	4.23	0.12

F.C: Nombre of citation; % C: Pourcentage of citation; Ic: Indice

3.4. Followed by participant observation

By this method we were able to deepen our investigation by being part of the context in which the patient is treated and his behavior towards the disease.

In the interview guide, the formulation of the questions is designed with regard to the patient model - plant and treatment period, more precisely around the evolution of the disease trajectory in response to the recommended Phytotreatment. In total, the 64 former patients mentioned during our surveys (n = 64), were particularly treated with plants, of which 43 patients received strict treatment by the healers. The reasons cited by these patients were the mainly exclusive relationship of trust which he seems to establish with the healers of the region and the native plants growing spontaneously on Djebel Zdimm.

Through these surveys and the most infected categories of the population, we were able to determine a predominance of LC in men (M) with a rate of 53.41 % against 46.59 % for women (F); the sex ratio M / F = 1.15).

Regarding the age groups we noticed that 51.27 % were a generation less than or equal to 15 years, followed by a second generation aged between 16 and 33 who represents 38.10 % of the affected population and 10.2 % older people greater than or equal to 34 years old.

From the results obtained, we note that the plants inventoried and used in the conventional treatment of cutaneous leishmaniasis (LC) are predominantly indigenous vascular species belonging to five botanical families; Asteraceae, Fabaceae, Zygophyllaceae, Apiaceae, Cupressaceae and Solanaceae with two cryptogamous species belonging to the family Lecanoraceae.

The choice of taxa, type of preparation and method of administration seems to be linked to the plant resources available locally in their environment, where Djebel Zdimm shelters 93 medicinal species belonging to 32 botanical families [28].

The seeds and leaves are the most used parts in the form of poultices applied directly to the abscesses on a regular basis until healing without

disfiguring scars. According to those surveyed, any wound treated by healers is healed regardless of its severity. The analysis of taxa (table 4), indicates the distinctive characteristics of plants used in the treatment of LC.

On the one hand, their high or even fatal toxicity such as *Peganum harmala* L. with 91 citations and *Carlina gummifera* (L.) Less. (CI = 59) *Deverra scoparia* Coss. (CI = 59). These taxa contain substances dangerous to health and their use must be limited or avoided, so the safe use of

medicinal plants has become a public health issue. On the other hand, the use of the cryptogamous species, *Lecanora esculenta* Evernsmann and *Rhizoplaca melanophthalma* (DC.)

Leuckert with 37 quotes constitute a typology of treatment of great heritage value reserved for healers who hold the empirical know-how of pest control treatment for lichens in within this steppe.

Table 4. Native antileishmanian species of the pharmacopoeia of the Semi-arid steppe of Setif

Species	Botanical family	Biological type *Floristic area	Part used	Traditional use	Application
<i>Carlina gummifera</i> (L.) Less.	<i>Asteraceae</i>	Chamaephyte *Méd	Root Latex	Ointment with camel fat	Local application
<i>Astragalus armatus</i> Willd. ssp. <i>tragacanthoides</i> (Desf.) Maire	<i>Fabaceae</i>	phanérophyte *End. N.A	Seeds Aerial part	Ointment with camel fat	Poultice
<i>Peganum harmala</i> L.	<i>Zygophyllaceae</i>	Chamaephyte *Irano-Tour-Eur	Seeds Root Leaves Flowers	-Fumigation -Aqueous extract - Ointment with <i>Pistacia Atlantica</i> oil	- Disinfect the abscess with smoke - Clean the abscess with a lotion - Poultice on dry or wet crusts
<i>Deverra scoparia</i> Coss.	<i>Apiaceae</i>	Chamaephyte *End.N.A	Fruit Flowers	- Trituration - Powder applied to the oil of <i>Olea europaea</i> or of <i>Pistacia Atlantica</i>	- Pad - Poultice
<i>Juniperus oxycedrus</i> L.	<i>Cupressaceae</i>	Phanérophyte *Atl-Circum- Méd	Seeds Fruit	- Ointment - Powder Mixed with honey	- Poultice
<i>Lycium arabicum</i> Boiss.	<i>Solanaceae</i>	Phanerophyte *E.Sah.	Seeds Leaves Fruit	- Fresh pounding- Powder mixture with:-honey - <i>Olea europaea</i> oil - Cade oil - Aqueous extract	- Pad - Poultice - Clean the abscess with a lotion
<i>Rhizoplaca melanophthalma</i> (DC.) Leuckert	<i>Lecanoraceae</i>	* Limestone rock Vulnerable calcareous species	Whole thallus	Pounding applied to <i>Pistacia atlantica</i> vegetable oil - with honey	- Poultice
<i>Lecanora esculenta</i> Evernsmann	<i>Lecanoraceae</i>	* Limestone rock Vulnerable calcareous species	Whole thallus	Pounding applied to the vegetable oil of <i>Pistacia atlantica</i> or the oil of <i>Olea europaea</i>	- Pad - Poultice

Abbreviations:* End. N. A: Endemic North Africa, Med: Mediterranean. Atl-Circum-Méd: Atlantique Circum, Mediterranean, Irano-Tour-Eur; Irano -Touranian -European. E.Sah: Eastern Sahara.

In the demarcated region, plant species with therapeutic properties have always been a major source for medicinal treatment, but they are not equal in the face of the exploitation of the villagers. Among these species, some of them have several medicinal properties, which has

widened the spectrum of their applications and their more or less abusive uses in traditional care (fig. 3).

This type of intensive and unreasoned exploitation can influence the evolution of plant potential and especially that of vulnerable species

which are experiencing a continuous decline in this ecosystem steppe. *Juniperus oxycedrus* and *Lycium arabicum* are reported as vulnerable to protected species [16]. *Rhizoplaca melanophthalma* and *Lecanora esculenta* are reported to be rare and endangered, currently these two species are only mentioned in Djebel Zdimm [15].

For the preservation of rare and endangered plants, they should only be exploited by good cultivation [29]. We note that these thallus species do not present ethnobotanical bibliographic data, they could be the subject of

additional studies, both chemically and biologically in order to isolate new antiparasitic compounds contained in these lichens. The sustainable development strategy for this ecosystem, which is both fragile and threatened with desertification [16], should aim to improve the health and socio-economic conditions of the demarcated Douars.

According to Ilbert et al. (2005) [30], the development models chosen, by associating local populations, will benefit from their empirical knowledge linked to medicinal plants.

a) *Lycium arabicum* Boiss., b) *Deverra scoparia* Coss., c) *Peganum harmala* L., d) *Astragalus armatus* Willd.

Fig. 3. Some leishmanicidal species used in the Setifian steppe (S. Chermat, 2017)

Conclusions

Following ethnobotany research carried out in the high Plains of Setif, eight medicinal species including two species of lichens, *Rhizoplaca melanophthalma* (DC.) Leuckert and *Lecanora esculenta* Evernsmann, have been inventoried for their antileishmania activity. Significant results for anti-leishmanicidal medicinal plants are bet for the first time in Algeria.

The semi-arid Setif steppe shows a great diversity in the antileishmanian uses held especially by the healers (Marabouts). Traditional knowledge provides leads for the development of

products, processes useful in the pharmacopoeia of HPS and sources of ecological information. This ancestral knowledge which will tends to disappear in the near future requires a more than essential preservation by integrating the plants which could constitute a means of testing this knowledge, for a better description, enhancement and preservation of the local pharmacopoeia pragmatically. This should take into account the vulnerability of plant resources in the sense of sustainable development by making the most of this promoter heritage, which will make it possible to effectively fight against leishmaniasis and other diseases.

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A 2019 STUDY ON DEOXYNIVALENOL AND ZEARALENONE LEVELS IN ROMANIAN BARLEY (*HORDEUM VULGARE L.*) SAMPLES

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Abstract: Mycotoxin contamination represents a clear public health concern. In this context, a barley survey was conducted in Romania, to monitor the occurrence of deoxynivalenol and zearalenone in barley samples collected during the 2019 growing season. A total number of 61 samples was collected along with information regarding the specific location of fields, applied agronomic practices and cropping systems. Enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) was used for the quantification of mycotoxins. The results identified Macroregion 3 (South-Muntenia development region) as the region with the highest number of contaminated samples above the maximum permitted level set by EC Commission Regulation No. 1881/2006, for both deoxynivalenol and zearalenone. These results highlight the importance of an effective and sustainable mycotoxin management along the food and feed chain, as well as the need of mapping the mycotoxin hotspot areas.

Keywords: barley, deoxynivalenol, zearalenone, Romania

1. Introduction

The Barley (*Hordeum vulgare L.*) is an important cereal, with an estimated global cultivated area of 48.82 million hectares and a production of 139.30 million tons in the 20018-2019 growing season (USDA, 2020). At European Union (EU) level, barley noted a cultivated area of 12,282.37 thousands hectares, which represented a harvested production of 63,612.59 thousands tones in 2019. During the same growing season, a cultivated area of 441.50 thousands hectares of barley noted a harvested production of 1,961.10 thousand tons in Romania (EUROSTAT, 2020).

Barley is a versatile cereal grain with a low glycemic index, having a rich nutlike flavour and an appealing chewy, pasta-like consistency. In addition to its robust flavour, barley is rich in vitamins, minerals and other beneficial plant compounds. However, as many other food products, cereals are susceptible to fungal attacks, both in the field and during storage (Zinedine et al., 2006; Tima et al., 2016; Stanciu et al., 2019). The fungi genus that should be taken into account for barley and other small grains is *Fusarium*, which is of great concern

because of the formation of mycotoxins, toxic secondary metabolites that pose a health risk to both humans and animals (Langseth and Elen, 1996; Malachova et al., 2010).

Deoxynivalenol (DON) and zearalenone (ZEA) are the most widely distributed mycotoxins produced by *Fusarium* species (Golge and Kabak, 2020; Langseth and Elen, 1996; Piacentini et al., 2015). They are predominantly produced by *Fusarium graminearum* and *F. culmorum*, which are frequently observed in temperate regions of Europe (EFSA, 2013; Golge and Kabak, 2020). DON can induce gastrointestinal symptoms such as vomiting both in humans and animals or acute and chronic effects such as immunosuppression, neurotoxicity, embryotoxicity and teratogenicity (Golge and Kabak, 2020; Wu et al., 2011). Given their highly toxigenic nature, at European level the presence of aflatoxins is strictly regulated, being imposed maximum levels in various commodities (EC Commission Regulation No. 1881/2006). The incidence of these mycotoxins in wheat and other cereals has been reported in many European countries, including Croatia (Pleadin et al., 2012), Czech Republic (Polišenská et al., 2008), Hungary (Tima et al.,

2016), Serbia (Jajić et al., 2008), Spain (Vidal et al., 2013) or Romania (Banu et al., 2011; Gagiú et al., 2018). However, there is little data about DON and ZEA content of barley in Romania.

In this context, the current study was undertaken to monitor the occurrence of DON and ZEA in barley samples collected during the 2019 harvests from fields located in various barley-producing Romanian counties. The information on mycotoxin levels in the Romanian counties will be essential to identify hotspot regions in Romania and will aid to design appropriate and cost-effective barley management strategies to prevent mycotoxin contamination right at the source, in order to promote safe and healthy food products.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Barley samples

The Sixty one ($n = 61$; 1 kg/sample) samples of barley were randomly collected in Romania in 2019 from private cereal farmers, immediately after harvest. The sampling was done by inspectors of the County Agriculture Directorates of the Romanian Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, according to the European guidelines (EC Commission Regulation No. 401/2006). Upon arrival, all samples were transferred into paper bags and stored in the dark until their assessment. All samples were received along with information regarding the specific location of fields and the applied agronomic practices (field location, type of barley cultivar, previous crops, incorporation of crop residues, sowing date, fertilisation and fungicide information etc.), which were filled in by farmers into a structured questionnaire dedicated to this study. In order to reference the origin of samples, the European nomenclature of territorial units for

statistics (NUTS) was used, based on the European regulation (EU Commission Regulation 2016/2066).

2.2. Mycotoxin analysis

A competitive enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) was selected for the quantitative analysis of DON and ZEA. The assessments were performed with commercially available test kits, according to the manufacturer's instructions (Ridascreen® DON and Ridascreen® Zearalenone, R-Biopharm AG, Germany), as previously described elsewhere (Smeu et al., 2020). The limit of detection of the ELISA kit for DON quantification was $18.50 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ and $1.75 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for ZEA, respectively. A mycotoxin quality control material was used for each measurement, to ensure the quality of the analyses (Trilogy Analytical Laboratory, Inc., USA).

2.3. Data analysis

ELISA tests were run in duplicate for each sample. Descriptive statistics (average and standard deviation) of these results have been employed in data analysis. Reported results include the recovery of the used quality control material. The extended uncertainty of the methods were $59.52 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for DON and $13.74 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for ZEA, respectively. Statistical analysis was performed using IBM® SPSS® Statistics 20 (IBM Corp., USA). Significance was defined at $P < 0.05$.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Origin of the collected samples

Barley samples were collected at the end of the 2019 growing season in major cereal-producing areas of Romania (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Distribution of the collected barley samples, 2019 harvest (NUTS III level)

A number of 61 barley samples was received for analysis in 2019. There were registered 14 samples (22.95%) from Macroregion 1 (North-West and Central development regions), 24 samples (39.34%) from Macroregion 2 (North-East and South-East development regions), 11 samples (18.03%) from Macroregion 3 (South-Muntenia and Bucharest-Ilfov development regions) and 12 barley samples (19.67%) from Macroregion 4 (South-West Oltenia and West development regions).

While there was received an average number of 2 barley samples from each County, Ialomița, Argeș and Teleorman (Macroregion 3), Vâlcea and Olt (Macroregion 4) counties noted only one barley sample for analysis. Galați County noted the highest number of samples (4 samples), followed by Brăila County, with 3 samples. There were received no barley samples from counties such as Bistrița-Năsăud, Maramureș, Satu-Mare, Harghita and Sibiu (Macroregion 1), Suceava and Constanța (Macroregion 2), Ilfov

(Macroregion 3), Hunedoara and Timiș (Macroregion 4).

3.2. Prevalence and distribution of DON contamination in barley samples in Romania

The analysis of 61 barley samples revealed that the 2019 harvest noted an important DON incidence, as a percent of 93.44 was attributed to the frequency of this mycotoxin for the assessed samples (Figure 2).

A contamination of 31.15% (19 samples) was noted for DON, where the registered mycotoxin concentrations were higher than the maximum permitted level ($1250.00 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) set by EC Commission Regulation No. 1881/2006 for unprocessed cereals other than durum wheat, oats and maize. Only 4 barley samples noted DON levels lower than the kit's limit of detection ($18.50 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$).

DON levels ranged from $11.93 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ to $1592.51 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ and there was noted a mean of $745.59 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 583.27 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$).

Fig. 2. Number of 2019 Romanian barley samples with different levels of deoxynivalenol concentrations

Macroregion 1 ($n = 14$) registered no barley sample with DON levels under the limit of detection of the ELISA kit ($18.50 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). The maximum permitted level of $1250.00 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ was exceeded by 7 barley samples (50%).

The North-West development region (6 samples) registered an average level of 1139.31

$\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 369.08 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), while the Central development region (8 samples) recorded an average of $1015.88 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 603.34 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$).

The maximum level of DON ($1579.96 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) noted in Macroregion 1 was determined for a barley sample from Covasna County (Central development region).

Macroregion 2 ($n = 24$) registered 4 barley sample with DON levels under the limit of detection of the ELISA kit, 14 samples with DON concentrations in the range of 18.51 – 500.00 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ and 3 samples with DON concentrations in the range of 500.01 – 1250.00 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$.

There were noted 3 samples (12.50%) which exceeded 1250.00 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ DON. The North-East development region (11 samples) registered an average level of 334.14 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 352.50 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), while the South-East development region (13 samples) recorded an average of 438.76 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 647.86 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). The maximum level of DON (1592.51 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) noted in Macroregion 2 was registered by a barley sample from Brăila County (South-East development region). This was also, the highest level of DON noted for the 2019 barley crop in Romania.

Macroregion 3 ($n = 11$) registered no barley sample with DON levels under 18.50 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. There were noted 5 samples (45.45%) from this region which exceeded the maximum admitted level. The South-Muntenia development region (11 samples) registered an average level of 866.02 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 644.65 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), while there were received no samples from the Bucharest-Ilfov development region. The maximum level of DON (1581.08 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) noted in Macroregion 3 was recorded by a barley sample from Dâmbovița County (South-Muntenia development region).

There were assessed 12 barley samples from Macroregion 4 geographical area. There was registered no barley sample with DON levels under 18.50 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. There was noted one sample with DON levels in the range of 18.51 – 500.00 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ and 7 samples with DON concentrations in the range of 500.01 – 1250.00 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. Also, 4 samples (33.33%) from this region exceeded the maximum admitted level.

The South-West Oltenia development region (8 samples) marked an average level of 797.64 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 274.24 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), while the West development region (4 samples) recorded an average of 1307.88 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 241.56 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). The maximum level of DON (1471.48 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) noted in Macroregion 4 was recorded by a barley

sample from Caraș Severin County (West development region).

In 2019, Dâmbovița County (Macroregion 3, South-Muntenia development region) was identified as the region with the highest average of DON contaminated samples, 1578.24 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 4.02 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$).

In South-Muntenia development region there were noted other 2 counties which scored average results which exceeded the DON limit imposed by the European regulations: Giurgiu County, with an average of 1395.30 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 130.23 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) and Teleorman County, with one barley sample which noted 1355.30 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. Thus, the southern area of Romania acted as a hotspot region for DON.

This should require implementation of DON management strategies to reduce mycotoxin contamination in the field, in order to result safe barley crops that will enhance trade and increase income and welfare of farmers and consumers.

A similar study noted an incidence of 83% of DON in barley samples in Czech Republic (Malachova et al., 2010). However, results of mycotoxin analyses reported from different countries are difficult to compare, due to various parameters such as climatic and pedological conditions, type of barley cultivar or applied agronomic practices which need to be taken into account (Langseth and Elen, 1996).

3.3. Prevalence and distribution of ZEA contamination in barley samples in Romania

Our study revealed that the 2019 harvest noted a lower incidence of ZEA within the assessed barley samples, as the frequency of this mycotoxin registered a percent of 65.57% (Figure 3).

Only 4 samples (6.56%) exceeded the threshold set by the European regulations, which stipulates 100.00 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ as the maximum level of ZEA for unprocessed cereals other than maize (EC Commission Regulation No. 1881/2006). Meanwhile, 21 barley samples (34.43%) noted ZEA levels lower than the kit's limit of detection (1.75 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). ZEA levels ranged from 0.01 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ to 137.37 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ and there was noted an average of 24.85 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 35.49 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$).

Fig. 3. Number of 2019 Romanian barley samples with different levels of zearalenone concentrations

Macroregion 1 ($n = 14$) noted 2 barley samples (14.29%) with ZEA levels under the limit of detection of the ELISA kit ($1.75 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). The maximum admitted level of $100.00 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ was not exceeded by any barley sample. The North-West development region (6 samples) registered an average level of $24.06 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 17.00 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), while the Central development region (8 samples) recorded an average of $37.25 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 32.42 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). The maximum level of ZEA ($96.94 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) noted in Macroregion 1 was determined for a barley sample from Braşov County (Central development region). The same sample exceeded the maximum admitted level of DON. Macroregion 2 ($n = 24$) registered 13 barley samples (54.17%) with ZEA levels under the limit of detection of the ELISA kit, 8 samples with ZEA concentrations in the range of $1.76 - 50.00 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ and 1 sample with ZEA concentrations in the range of $50.01 - 100.00 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. There were determined 2 samples (8.33%) which exceeded $100.00 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ZEA. The North-East development region (11 samples) registered an average level of $3.99 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 4.34 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), while the South-East development region (13 samples) recorded an average of $24.40 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 46.65 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). The maximum level of ZEA ($137.37 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) noted in Macroregion 2 was registered by a barley sample from Brăila County (South-East development region). This was also, the highest level of DON noted for the 2019 barley crop in Romania.

Macroregion 3 ($n = 11$) recorded 3 barley samples with ZEA levels under $1.75 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. There were noted 2 samples (18.18%) from this region which exceeded the maximum admitted level. The South-Muntenia development region (11 samples) registered an average level of $38.60 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 44.44 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). The maximum level of ZEA ($120.12 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) noted in Macroregion 3 was recorded by a barley sample from Dâmboviţa County (South-Muntenia development region). The same sample noted the maximum level of DON in Macroregion 3. In Macroregion 4 geographical area (12 barley samples), there were registered 3 samples (25.00%) with ZEA levels under $1.75 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. There were noted 5 samples with ZEA concentrations in the range of $1.76 - 50.00 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ and 4 samples with ZEA concentrations in the range of $50.01 - 100.00 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. There were no samples that exceeded $100.00 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ZEA. The South-West Oltenia development region (8 samples) marked an average level of $13.63 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 20.38 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), while the West development region (4 samples) recorded an average of $57.01 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 36.87 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). The maximum level of ZEA ($93.55 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) noted in Macroregion 4 was recorded by a barley sample from Caraş-Severin County (West development region). The same sample exceeded the maximum admitted level of DON.

Macroregion 3 noted the highest average level of ZEA. However, the West development region (Macroregion 4) registered the highest average

level of this mycotoxin, in between the Romanian NUTS II development regions. At NUTS III level, Dâmbovița County (Macroregion 3, South-Muntenia development region) was identified as the region with the highest average of ZEA contaminated samples, $112.65 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 10.57 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). The same County noted the highest average DON level. Other counties which noted high ZEA average concentrations were Caraș Severin (Macroregion 4, West development region), which noted $80.67 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 18.21 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), followed by Giurgiu County (Macroregion 3, South-Muntenia development region), that registered a ZEA average concentration of $55.83 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($\pm 36.53 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) for its samples.

Our study shows a significant lower incidence of ZEA than DON in the assessed barley samples. However, the frequency of this mycotoxin was 65.57%. A similar report which studied the occurrence of DON and ZEA in cereal and cereal products from Turkey noted that barley, bulgur and other selected products did not contain ZEA (Golge and Kabak, 2020).

Conclusions

This 2019 barley survey has been aimed at extending knowledge on the occurrence of DON and ZEA mycotoxins in various barley cultivars across Romania. Our results indicated that barley is a potential source of DON exposure in certain regions of Romania. Hotspot regions for DON were identified in various areas but only when environmental conditions were favourable for the occurrence of toxigenic fungi. As for the ZEA levels, there was noted that barley samples which recorded high levels of ZEA also registered concentrations of DON which most of the times were over the maximum admitted level ($1250.00 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), according to the European regulations (EC Commission Regulation No. 1881/2006).

Thus, for an efficient mycotoxin management, it is recommended to investigate the multi-mycotoxin occurrence in Romanian barley samples. Also, further monitoring studies are also needed to estimate the mycotoxins occurrence levels for other types of cereals cultivated in Romania.

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DESIGN PRINCIPLES FOR ASSURING FOOD SAFETY IN ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN DAIRY FARMS

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Abstract: Milk is obtained in all countries of the European Union and occupies an important place in the economy of the Member States. In Romania the raising of dairy cows is a tradition among the inhabitants of rural and mountain areas. As far as exports were concerned, Romania was ranked 29th in the list of exporters of cow milk worldwide and ranked 19th among importers. In this frame, food safety in dairy farms it is a no-negotiable problem that must be assured by the mountain farmers. The paper presents the main hygienic criteria and some design methods that must accomplish and some technical solutions to be implemented in order assure food safety in dairy mountain farm. The main guidelines processed for this study were: EN 1672-2: 2005 Food processing machinery – Basic concepts – Part 2: Hygienic Requirements EN ISO 14159: 2004 Safety of machinery – Hygiene requirements for the design of machinery

Keywords: food safety, dairy, mountain farms

1. Introduction

The basic general food rules are formulated in the Framework Regulation (EC) 178/2002 for foodstuffs. For Romanian national legislation, this meant major renewals since the rules on food law had to be adapted from the Romanian Foodstuffs Act to the Food and Feed Code [4]. This regulation also set the establishment and functions of the European Food Safety Authority.

This EU agency collaborates with national authorities to ensure food safety, to ensure that unsafe food is not placed on the market, to ensure traceability and to achieve long-term cumulative effects [1, 2].

The problem of food safety has many aspects regarding equipments, technology, food plant design etc.

The manufacturer of food equipments are responsible for their quality. By this the manufacturer to follow the relevant legislations, as well as the corresponding standards and publications of state of the art for each installation [12, 14].

The food plant designers and constructors are responsible for the quality of the plant and have to follow the corresponding regulations, as well as standards and publications according to the state of the art [13]. This applies to the entire

system area, related to apparatus and components, its installation and function and its ability to clean.

The user of food machines, the product manufacturer, is responsible for the product quality and has to follow the corresponding regulations, as well as standards and publications according to the state of the art for the entire process area, for the production, the product, the personnel and the cleaning. HACCP and GMP in particular apply.

In the sense of all that has been mentioned, the paper presents some issues related to food safety assurance in mountain dairy farms.

2. Hygienic design criteria for mountain dairy farms

The fundamental cause for implementing hygienic design principles is to prevent contamination of food products. Equipments and factories with a poor hygienic design are difficult to clean. Residues (soil) may be retained in crevices and dead areas.

Product residues allow micro-organisms present in the product to survive and multiply. Residues of cleaning and disinfection chemicals increase the risk of corrosion and may cross-contaminate subsequent batches of product.

Additionally, contaminants, e.g. foreign matter, allergens, lubricants, detergents and disinfectants, might be carried with the product during processing and packaging.

The primary goal of installations and factory design is to accomplish engineering requests. Many times the requirements of hygienic design dispute with the functionality. An acceptable compromise must never endanger food safety.

It is more effective to incorporate hygienic claims into the initial design because upgrading an existing design can be extremely expensive and may fail cleanability [3].

3. Materials used for building dairy equipment

All used materials in the construction of dairy equipment must be non-toxic. It must not adulterate the food by distributing harmful substances, nor affect its sensory characteristics. Surely, milk contact materials must not contain lead, arsenic, cadmium, or mercury as intended ingredients.

In general, aluminum is not sufficiently resistant to corrosion and should be avoided on contact with food. Zinc coated substrates are not recommended. If nickel or chrome plated equipment is used, the plating must be reliably manufactured and its integrity must be checked regularly to ensure that it does not use or contaminate the product. Chemically plated materials are preferred over galvanizing due to their greater durability and more compact and dense surface layers. Plastics can be used to exclude metal-to-metal contact (eg. for load-bearing surfaces), as guides and covers, or for hoses due to their plasticity and corrosion resistance, but it should be noted that some plastics are porous and can absorb product constituents and port microorganisms.

Therefore they should be avoided or if they have to be used for functional reasons, special cleaning procedures and periodical inspections are necessary. Materials that have been modified with antimicrobial chemicals should not be considered as a substitute for hygienic design. Micro-organisms may build up resistance to such chemicals over a period of time. In addition the effect of these antimicrobial substances will only be in direct contact to the micro-organisms. If they are embedded by soil, the modified material will not act as a disinfectant. Rubber materials and other elastomers that are commonly used for gaskets, seals and scrapers, etc. they can be

damaged by excessive mechanical or thermal compression or by severe deformation [9].

Wood is appropriate only in a limited number of cases (for example, when it assists in relative humidity regulation and/or microbiological ecology such as when ripening cheese or producing wines and vinegar, etc.). Wooden surfaces must be cleaned effectively and disinfected because they can retain micro-organisms which can subsequently grow in the presence of product nutrients.

The materials selected should not render the equipment difficult to clean and to disinfect and so their surfaces must be non-porous, smooth and free of cracks, fissures, scratches and pits that can shelter and retain soil and / or microorganisms after cleaning. As a general rule, the contact surfaces with the product should have a finish of 0.8 μm Ra or better and be free from imperfections such as potholes, creases and cracks in the final fabricated form [5, 9].

Under the intended conditions of use, including cleaning regimes, materials (and coatings) should have adequate resistance to corrosion, stress, fatigue, impact, wear, abrasion and erosion, etc. It is worth noting that welding can produce less smooth surfaces than those of their base metal and requires post-welding treatments, such as sanding or polishing.

In general, stainless steels offer excellent corrosion resistance and are therefore widely used in the food industry. The range of available stainless steels is wide, but the choice of the most appropriate class will depend on the intended conditions of use, as well as the requirements to which the steel will be subjected and the requirements of processing, formability, weldability, hardness and cost. [9].

Dairy processing installations must be easy to clean and maintain, and must protect the products from contamination. In the case of aseptic equipment, it must be sterilisable and must prevent the ingress of micro-organisms (i.e. it must be bacteria tight), assessed by test methods. It must be possible to monitor and control all its functions which are critical from a microbiological safety point of view.

4. Hygienic design and construction

4.1 Joints

In addition to the hygienic design criteria described, specific requirements for closed equipment include the following elements.

It is strongly recommended that the number of joints, whether welded or detachable, is minimized. Bending of pipes is highly preferable to the use of prefabricated bends which have to be installed using joints. Welding is the preferred method of joining, provided that it is done correctly, to ensure a smooth and continuous weld. Where detachable joints are unavoidable, they must be hygienically sealed [6].

Requirements for detachable joints include:

- coaxial alignment of the two mating bores,
- an axial stop for controlled compression of the seal,
- room for thermal expansion of the seal,
- avoidance of sharp edges such that seals are not damaged,
- free from crevices.

The connections shown on the left allow misalignment and do not control the compression of the seal. The connections on the right comply with the hygienic design requirements. Improper alignment due to poor design results in inadequate cleaning and reduced drainability. Improper alignment can be eliminated by good design of the coupling, but this may require reduced clearances and greater accuracy during assembly.

Metal to metal joints (other than welds) seal as a result of the deformation of the contacting metal surfaces. When these surfaces are permanently damaged as a consequence, it becomes more difficult to obtain a tight seal after each disconnection. Even when these joints do not show visible leaks, it is possible for microorganisms to enter.

Furthermore, the seal obtained is very unlikely to be continuous at the interface with the product. More likely, the actual seal follows an irregular line between the inside and outside. The resulting annular crevice will trap product. Therefore, these metal to metal joints must not be used in hygienic plant pipelines.

4.2 Static Seal design

In addition to the hygienic design criteria described specific requirements for seals include the following:

- installations containing conventionally designed grooves (e.g. right-angled O-ring seats) invariably create gaps and crevices that are impossible to clean in-place and/or to sterilize in-line. One cause is that elastomers have significantly higher thermal

expansion coefficients than steel. Examples of expansion coefficients are:

- Steel 15 - 18 (10⁻⁶/°C)
- NBR 110 - 210 (10⁻⁶/°C)
- EPDM 160 - 190 (10⁻⁶/°C)
- FKM 150 - 200 (10⁻⁶/°C)
- FFKM 300 - 350 (10⁻⁶/°C)

During heating the seal will expand to cover an increasingly larger surface of steel, protecting microorganisms trapped between the seal and the steel surface against contact with hot water, chemical solution or steam.

After cooling down and shrinkage of the seal, the surviving micro-organisms may be released and will multiply and contaminate the product [7].

Additionally, repeated thermal expansion of the seal into the product flow may result in it suffering damage which will not only contaminate the product but may also progressively reduce its ability to seal again upon re-cooling.

O-rings can be acceptable from a hygienic point of view if mounted in a way that ensures that the area of steel covered by the rubber at the product side is not influenced by thermal expansion. Often this leads to large forces inside the O-ring and as a result the lifetime of the O-ring may be reduced significantly.

The dimensions of the O-ring and the design of the groove to be used for mounting sensors for example are critical to achieving controlled compression of the seal [11]. The O-ring in such an application needs periodic maintenance with an inspection of the O-ring upon dismantling. Used O-rings should not be re-installed.

Over-compression of seals may affect the hygienic characteristics of equipment in two ways. Firstly, over compression may lead to destruction of the seal, particularly if it is heated (such as during hot cleaning and/or sterilization).

The seal may exceed the maximum compression caused by thermal expansion and may become brittle and malfunction, while its particles may break and contaminate the product. Second, over-compression can lead to the seal protruding into the product flow, thus preventing cleaning and leakage.

Under-compression is also highly undesirable as it may lead to both indentations and crevices and failure to provide a reliable seal. Even when it is not visibly leaking, the seal may permit the ingress of micro-organisms.

For aseptic equipment bacteria tightness of seals is essential. For static seals, their materials

should be resilient enough to ensure an adequate seal under all conditions of intended use. Consequently, attention must be given to thermal expansion at high temperatures (e.g. during hot cleaning and sterilization) and to loss of resilience at low temperatures (e.g. during the manufacture of ice cream).

Materials that have insufficient resilience and which expand significantly more than stainless steel, such as polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE, expansion coefficient approx. $100 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$, compared to approx. $16 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ for stainless steel) may change shape as a result of heating. In a proper design, the material will not provide a tight seal anymore after cooling down.

4.3 Dynamic seals

Dynamic seals (reciprocating and rotating) are lubricated by the product which may be transported past the seal and back again, contaminating further product. Due to this, single dynamic seals which will not prevent the passage of micro-organisms are not suitable for every application.

They may, even if properly designed, be easy to clean but not bacteria tight. Care must be taken that dynamic seals can be cleaned. The narrow annular space which is usually found at the product side in the proximity of the seal must be avoided. The space around the seal should be as wide as possible.

Single dynamic seals must be avoided in aseptic equipment. Effective sealing may be achievable by using bellows or diaphragms that separate the seal from the product side. Where this is not possible (e.g. in the case of rotary seals), double seals must be used.

The space between the seals must be flushed with a sterile fluid (e.g. condensate, sterile water or steam) to scavenge micro-organisms that enter the space between the seals. Which flushing fluid should be used will depend on the product and the process.

To avoid the transfer of micro-organisms into the product area the distance between the two seals must always be larger than the stroke of the reciprocating shaft. It should also be noted that rotating shafts may exhibit some axial mobility allowing the passage of micro-organisms [8].

4.5 Drainability

Care must be taken to ensure that any closed process line can be completely drained. The pipes should be inclined 3° towards the drain points. Even smooth construction can prevent leakage.

Although for concentric pipes a concentric reducer is fully acceptable, this is not possible for horizontal pipes where a concentric reducer would prevent complete drainage if the flow is in the wrong direction. For horizontal pipes, eccentric reducers are preferred.

In addition, gearboxes should be long enough to avoid shaded areas. To avoid dead areas in the equipment, it is recommended to avoid the use of closed-ended tees. If this is not possible, short right angle tees or so-called "swept tees" can be used. Sweep tees should be used with caution, however, as a sweep tee in a horizontal pipe could prevent leakage. Sharp corners should be avoided. All interior angles and corners should be well rounded to facilitate cleaning.

4.6 Screw threads

Exposed screw threads should not be used at the product side. If the use of screwed connections is unavoidable, such as for the attachment of pump impellers to drive shafts, the hygienic design principles should be used. Where possible at the product side welding should be used, following the guidelines for hygienic welds. An acceptable alternative might be the use of adhesives.

If adhesives are used, care must be taken to ensure that the bond obtained is reliable, hygienic, and can withstand process and cleaning conditions. Additionally, the adhesive must be approved for food contact applications [10].

4.7 Thermal insulation

Pipe work can be insulated by venting air into the casing of a double-walled pipe. This is a very effective way to meet hygienic design criteria. If a vacuum is not used, a chloride-free insulating material should be used, such as the appropriate qualities of rock wool. The insulating material must be covered by a completely welded stainless steel outer tube to prevent the ingress of air and moisture.

Such ingress could promote corrosion between the walls, assisted by possible microbial growth. Ultimately, this will result in leaks, allowing micro-organisms to contaminate the product. The same principles apply to the insulation of process vessels which should also be enclosed.

Depending on the duty of the tank, it may be necessary to provide a filtered vent hole to prevent unacceptable pressures between the inner and the outer walls (e.g. during sterilization) and maintain the hygienic integrity of the insulation.

Conclusions

Assuring food safety in romanian mountain dairy farms can be ensured by a proper layout of the farm, using the proper material, and automatization of the key process variables.

A series of measures to prevent the risk of mixing pasteurized and non-pasteurized product must be implemented.

Also, the process equipment of the must have a hygienic design and therefore be cleanable, possibly for disinfection / sanitization and bacterial tightness.

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NEW HORIZONS IN THE FOOD ACT: TISSUE ENGINEERING AND PRODUCTION OF BIOCELLULAR FOOD

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Abstract: *The study brings into discussion one of the most daring research directions that has passed from the laboratory phase to the industrial phase, especially in USA and Israel, with potential in China too but, even though the idea is an European one, it is insignificant in the activity of our continent. We talk about an alternative that we consider COMPLEMENTARY and NOT a substitute to conventionally food production. There are approached aspects of the new **tissue engineering** with applicability in obtaining **natural cellular food** in laboratory, on the principles of Cellular Agriculture. As objectives of the paper we mention the making of a DIAGNOSIS regarding food manner in relation to the development of the human society and especially to science and technology linked to alimentation. There are highlighted elements of the new demarche of **Tissue Engineering** on direction of **bio cellular food** production, being analyzed aspects of cellular biology, of the development genetics and a series of techniques linked to the obtaining of tissues by cellular multiplication. There is analyzed the place and part of bio cellular food in mankind evolution, taking into consideration physiological, psychological and cultural factors of the food act, but also gastronomic revolutions that have accompanied food manner along history.*

Keywords: *alimentation, biology, cell, food, living tissue.*

1. Introduction

It is known that the first agrarian revolution (almost 12000 years ago) has meant the beginning of agriculture and of the Agricultural society that has in fact gone on until now. At present we are practically facing the second agrarian revolution (after the year 2000), namely the obtaining of *cellular agri-zoo-food* products, i.e. natural (biological) ones, but produced in laboratories.

Although shocking for the present mentality, it is a fascinating demarche, which represents a **change that will probably bring a new worldwide order (!)**. As we all may observe, the world is changing, and within this context the question: “How will the world feed in the future?” becomes legitimate.

A largely accepted scenario [18, 20, 25, 28], unless major cataclysms interfere, refers to the fact that until 2030 Terra’s population will reach approximately 8,5 billion people, and up to 2050,

almost 9,7 billions, situation when food problem will become extremely severe. It is clear that FOOD must exist for all these billions, without exhausting planet resources, provided that already in the present mankind is confronted with huge problems. On the other hand, the fact that technologies will evolve must be taken into consideration.

Among the problems we are already confronted with are those directly linked to the food act, such as: drinking water crisis, climate changes, in extension extreme poverty (over a billion people are still living out of 1,9 dollars daily) and other. To be added at this FOOD WASTE where at world level almost 1/3 from food intended for human consumption is thrown away every year, in an estimated amount of 1, 3 billion tones [7, 13, 27, 29].

To avoid crises is a major preoccupation, especially concerning food security, a work direction being to analyze how to solve ecosystem disharmonies. And this especially concerning biodiversity reduction and, implicitly,

the loss of genetic resources with alimentary potential.

Consequently to the growth of the anthropic impact there also appears the undesired situation of natural genetic modification of microorganisms, to which is added virus and bacteria vehicular via animals (including the farm ones), the result being pandemic apparition [4, 24, 30, 31]. The food crises may also be due to environment pollution, which will have irreversible consequences, also following the use of pesticides and animal intensive-industrial breeding.

Obligated by the demographic growth, concomitantly with accentuated impoverishment of natural resources, as a starting point in the food analyses we take into consideration the HYPOTHESIS to modify people's mentality concerning feeding mode and to find afferent technical solutions. For example, if we refer to the food act finality, one can notice a new paradigmatic element, which is **nutrition of precision** that represents in fact „a personalized diet + *omics* sciences” (metabolomics, proteomics etc.).

All these general ideas linked to the food act induce a series of questions concerning food at present and in the future, as well as HOW TO PROVIDE FOOD: - Will future food look like the today one? - Will we eat more? – We will consume less and of a better quality? – Will we feed us differently, with „cellular food”, produced *in vitro*, in laboratories? – Will we feed us with synthetic food too? – Do we consider the problem statically or dynamically? Meaning, do we take into consideration the „normal” situation (balance) or the incipient or deep food crisis situation? - What will be financial interests? – Why specialists' opinions are divergent? etc. etc.

Taking into consideration all these questions, it is obvious that the present manner of thinking (imprinted habits along time, all food psychology), need a CHANGE OF PARADIGM. Of course it is difficult to accept this change, which imposes serious explanations and in essence constitute the paper **general objective**.

Besides the general objective, the paper also proposes **special objectives**, respectively:

- To accomplish a DIAGNOSIS regarding the feeding mode in relation to the development of

the human society and especially of the science and technology linked to alimentation;

- To highlight the new TISSULAR ENGINEERING demarche [22, 26] and some aspects of the technologic flow on direction of producing *BIOCELLULAR FOOD*.

2. Methodology and concept

There is approached the analyses of certain aspects of *cellular biology*, of certain elements of development genetics, as well as the highlight of certain techniques on direction of *tissue engineering* linked to cellular multiplication, to afferent culture medium and used bioreactors.

Methodologically, we underline the IDEA that *stem cells may divide, keeping intact their ADN, almost indefinitely long time*. Moreover, starting from their genetic information there may be obtained *specialized cells*, such as muscular cells or adipose ones.

3. Results and discussions

The future food may be a combination between certain elements of the present production systems and the accomplishment of natural food obtained by laboratory methods, with the help of the scientific and technical demarche of the tissue engineering.

TISSULAR ENGINEERING represents the multidisciplinary scientific demarche that includes biotechnology, development genetics, medicine and engineering, aiming to **naturally** promote human life quality by reestablishing, maintaining, improving or *RENEWING the function of biologic tissues or organs*, having as a pre-established objective to make natural food out of *living cells (biocells)*, respectively the generically named category:
BIOCELLULAR FOOD.

Of course, the change of paradigm is not an aim in itself, but a fortuitous passing, as we may see what is going on in the world today. Now the change becomes possible following the technological development of the 21st century (table 1).

Table 1. Phases of paradygmatic change regarding the food mode

No.	PHASES	SPECIFICATION
1.	Alimentary mentality	<p>For the transition phase in the mentality of the feeding mode there are looked for COMPLEMENTARY alternatives and NOT replacing ones.</p> <p>An idea to be followed in the new paradigm is to pass mentality from food obtained by „metabolic processes”, to those obtained by „cellular processes”:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complex <i>morphogenesis</i> of the tissues in embryonic development (in conformity with development genetics) may be replicated or repeated in TISSULAR ENGINEERING in postnatal tissues, including with applications in food production. <p>Among techniques to obtain food in the new paradigms we mention: <i>extracts, MGO, 3D, in vitro, Nano-food in capsules etc.</i></p>
2.	Concepts and techniques of the tissue engineering	<p>We speak about a multidisciplinary field that, by reestablishing, maintaining and improving the tissue or organ function, starts from the CELL level (that constitutes basic elements of the used systems in tissue engineering) on two directions :</p> <p>(a) ON BIOENGINEERING DIRECTION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Theoretic and methodologic interdisciplinarity between biology and technical sciences: medical engineering of tissues / biomechanics / genetic engineering etc. <p>(b) ON BIOTECHNOLOGY DIRECTION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ utilization in microorganism technique, of <i>cultures of vegetal and animal cells</i> with applications in agriculture, food industry, the chemist’s one etc.

From what is presented it clearly appears that „raw material” in tissue engineering and in organic tissue generation is represented by **living cells** (fig.1).

Fig.1. Principle classification concerning the cell types from different fields

Up to this moment, the largest practical applicability is in *bio cellular medicine*, where research activities are oriented on specific themes of cellular biology, as for example:

- study of water transportation through erythrocyte membrane;

- cell ultrastructural analyses in pathological and experimental conditions;

- *polioxometalites* study with biomedical applications [1,9,12].

The essence of the idea, in everything that has been enumerated, and not only, are **BIOCELLS**,

which also interests concerning the evolution of the alimentary act.

We recall that „cell” denomination comes from the latin „*cella*”, term introduced by *Robert Hooke* (1635-1703) following observations made through microscope, he being known as the father of microscopy. Here it is from this first step, 300 years after, it has come to industrial technologies of the cell multiplication process [28]. Before seeing the role, the place and the mode of technical action concerning the utilization and **cell multiplication**, we consider it opportune to analyze the most pregnant limitative factor too, which is our psychological conservatism. Reality (to see climate changes, pandemics, demography, environment protection, tendency towards sustainable technologies etc.),

beyond our desires, „joys”, habits, will push us towards the **change of paradigm** regarding food production and food mode too, where in principle, beyond the mentioned factors, we will have to pass FROM HEDONISM TO PRAGMATISM. By analyzing things from biotechnological perspective on applicative direction in „*vegetable crops & animal production & food*”, i.e. the responsible field for the food act, we may extract data that lead to the necessity of paradigm change [2,5,13,14]. On their basis, in our opinion, we consider that paradigm change will impose a series of significant conceptual modifications in the „*Farm to Fork Strategy*”, both in the vegetal production, and especially in the production of animal origin food (see the box).

Paradigm shift in animal husbandry:

- CLASSICAL „METABOLIC” ANIMAL HUSBANDRY on principles of the **BIOECONOMIC ZOOTECHNY** (that include environment in the equation), with technical basis in genetic stimulation and improvement on *biodiversity* and traditionalism line, having as a pre-established target animal product QUALITY and mostly applied in fragile zones (of mountain, in wet zones, the isolated ones and other), is
Complementary with
- BIOCELLULAR ANIMAL HUSBANDRY or **BIOCELLULAR ZOOTECHNY** (it also with natural food production, but obtained in the laboratory), that slowly becomes a replacement of intensively-industrial technologies of animal breeding and of farms with a large number of animals in a reduced space, will follow the QUANTITY principles, meaning production yield growth, but also substantial protection of natural environment.

Although the problem is vast, in this paper we propose to achieve a „putting the problem” in connection to **biocellular food production**. We again must mention that the field is in full forward on international plan, which should represent a landmark for Romania’s food strategy too.

3.1. Biocellular food

INTUITION: „ In the future we will get rid of the absurdity of breeding an entire chicken in order to eat its breast or wing, breeding these parts separately under an adequate environment” — Winston Churchill, 1931.

A short HISTORY shows *W. Churchill*’s premonition, but also Europe as a starting point of the idea to produce food using cell cultures. The idea belongs to the Dutch *Willem van Eelen* who, at the beginning of the 50’s of the twentieth century, began to work at the elaboration of a technology with commercial

potential. It was a work for life and a life’s time fight to persuade the people around him that his ideas weren’t chimeras but things that may radically change the manner mankind may provide food easier than by traditional agriculture. In the year 1999, at 76 years old, *van Eelen* gets: the international brevet for meat industrial production using cellular cultures [25,28]. It is the moment when practically from the scientific universe it has moved on to the technological one and, more than that, a new productive field of activity has been validated, *de facto* certifying biocellular food.

BIOCELLULAR FOOD represents to obtain natural food delocalized from territorial landscape, produced by laboratory methods that are based on the process of living cell multiplication, both vegetal and especially animal ones, they being of greater economic and ecologic interest.

Of course all these couldn't have evolved unless cellular biology hadn't remarkably developed, that managed to reveal laws of vital process development at the level of cellular organs through two important branches, of interest for cellular multiplication, namely: cytology and cytophysiology [3,27]. It is obvious that, for certain stages of the food act, „cellular multiplications” are applicable. In this regard, if we generalize, we consider that we may speak about a new technical-scientific demarche, namely, about **biocellular agro-zootechny**, known under the generic denomination of „Cellular Agriculture”.

CELLULAR AGRICULTURE is an emergent field that produces animal products out of cellular culture, rather than animals as such. This field is based on biotechnology progresses and at the moment informs food science about products that contain proteins, such as milk and eggs, as well as food based on tissue, such as meat and fish [8,11,16,17,19].

As major objectives of cellular agriculture one may mention: **food sustainable production and food security**. These ones have inspired a growing interest on behalf of different disciplines, from industrial biotechnology, synthetic biology, materials science and tissue engineering, up to social sciences, history, philosophy and art / design. As research direction of cellular agriculture at international level we observe the theme: „**Biotechnology for sustainable food**”. On this direction key *technologic researches* include proteins and lipids production using fermentation technologies, cellular scaffolding, formulation of culture medium, projection of specific bioreactors, operation of bio printing, as well as amplitude conditions necessary in industrial scale production. Thus it becomes opportune, in order to understand as correctly as possible the place of biocellular food in the complementarity of the food act, to analyze the food diversity, food typology and the one of agri-food assortments (table 2).

Table 2. *The place of biocellular food in food diversity (biodiversity, diversity of processing and marketing)*

TYPE OF GENERAL FOODS		FOOD CATEGORIES	GROUPS OF FOODS
NATURAL FOODS	Obtained through METABOLIC processes in ontogenesis	PRIMARY FOODS (coming from agriculture)	Agricultural products
		INDUSTRIAL FOODS (coming from food industry)	Processed industrial food
	Obtained by CELLULAR processes	NATURAL FOODS IN VITRO	Food of cellular agriculture, in which “BIOCELLULAR FOOD” is obtained
PROJECTED FOODS (natural or artificial ones)	CLASSICAL INNOVATIVE <u>NATURAL</u> FOOD		Composite industrial food
			Complex food (dishes)
			Hyper-complex food (menus)
	INNOVATIVE <u>NATURAL</u> FOODS BY BIODIVERSITY CAPITALIZATION		Group of traditional food (with little known local specific)
			Group of insects (probably food of the future)
			Group of fish and aquaculture
			Group of aquatic vegetation
			Group of genetically modified food genetic
	HEALTH GENERATING INNOVATIVE <u>NATURAL</u> FOODS		Functional composite food
			Excellent complex foods /Functional ones
			Functional hyper-complex foods
			Medicinal foods
			Fortified cellular <u>natural</u> foods, which we may call: „FUNCTIONAL BIOCELLULAR FOOD”
INNOVATIVE <u>ARTIFICIAL</u> FOODS		Synthetic foods (NB – pay attention to composition / danger degree)	
		Pseudo-synthetic foods, including stable semi-synthetic life forms.	

As *advantages* of obtaining biocellular food there may be mentioned a series of aspects. For example, the cellular culture meat is clean, doesn't contain drug residues or hormones used to ensure large productions from conventional agriculture and there are not made genetic manipulations at the level of meat cells.

Another example shows that biocellular food production doesn't need any more the agricultural surfaces that ensure plant growth for animal feeding. **Biocellular food is absolutely natural**, having in addition also spectacular advantages, such as those linked to ethic and religion (rabies have declared it *kosher* meat and this is a signal linked to its religious impact), going up to economy of vital resources. Economic and ecologic estimations are extremely encouraging.

Thus, in conformity with a study [CB Insights, 2017], the ground surface used for cellular culture meat represents 1% of the one used for conventional meat, the water consumption represents 18% and the gas emission with effect on carbon footprint 20%.

More, obtaining meat without sacrificing animals has already become reality, and research in this zone has made that products from cellular culture meat reach competitive prices (as I mentioned before, the champions being the USA, Japan and Israel, with great potential in China).

Although we consider that it is necessary to deepen the issues, it seems that productivity is spectacular by the estimates made [Good Food Institute, 2018], studies showing that „10 pork stem cells may produce 50.000 tons of meat in two months” (!).

In this context, the impact on medium term upon industry is huge. It is forecast an occupation in the field of cellular food of 26% from the global workforce, reaching a global business figure of over 6 trillion dollars.

3.2. Technological stages in obtaining biocellular food

The technologic process (based on principles of tissue engineering) in order to obtain biocellular food has 3 basic stages: (1) tissue sampling; (2) stem cell selection and multiplication; (3) process of directing in stem cell specialization and growth of the new tissue in a desired shape.

- **Stage 1:** Everything begins by sampling a small muscular tissue from the organism which is wanted to be transformed in cellular culture meat. It is a very similar procedure to the sampling of a biopsy sample.
- **Stage 2:** From the respective tissue there are separated *stem cells* that are fed *in vitro* and multiplied in a reactor, transformed in *specialized cells* (as for example by making muscular cells and tissue).
- **Stage 3:** Specialized cells follow the technological process of *meat* making, being afterwards sown in a collagen bed where they are bread, giving them the wanted shape (using a special medium using a special environment).

3.3. Applications to obtain biocellular food

• Technology used to make a piece of meat mass for roast meat

The most developed scientific and production direction of making biocellular food is to obtain meat [6,10,14]. As cells may only develop with a thickness of approximately 0,5 mm in culture, it is easier to „breed” minced meat than something too thick, such as a piece of roast meat. Of course it is also taken into consideration the taste (A), i.e. muscular cells might be cultivated on *beads* that offer a large surface in a *bioreactor*. When muscular cells are eliminated, the muscle will already have hamburger consistence (B), with adequate nutritive value, as it is observed in figure 2.

Fig.2. Biocellular food in various forms, as for example roast meat (A), hamburger (B)

A series of imagistic examples [15,17] are offered beginning with *Prof. Mark Post* (Maastricht University), who is known for having

created a first burger in laboratory in the year 2013, and then by making different gastronomic plateaus (fig. 3).

A.

B.

Fig.3. Burger type biocellular food (A) and roast from „cultivated meat” (B)

- *The technology used in order to make a mass of protein liquid, as milk for example* The respective technique is described as an image in figure 4.

Milk is usually obtained from mother-cows kept under lactation in an industrial framework (A). In exchange, we may make the SAME MILK using a culture that „consumes” simple sugars in order to make proteins from milk (B).

Fig. 4. Technology used to make natural bio cellular milk

• **Technology used to make fish meat „cultivated” in the laboratory**

To obtain the mass of bio cellular fish product presupposes several work phases [21, 23]:

Phase 1. – Cell sampling from muscular tissue at fish (ex. tuna etc.) and different living sea creatures, anesthetized ones.

Phase 2. – The extracted sample is treated with stem cells and enzymes.

Phase 3. – The sample is placed in a bioreactor where cells are fed with a solution of vitamins, mineral salts, lipids, sugars, proteins from plants and amino acids; in these conditions offered by the bioreactor and the culture environment, the original cells (therefore, natural ones) have the possibility of rapid multiplication.

Phase 4. – The solution rich in fish cells is placed in a spin in order to separate the tissue, freshly

grown in bioreactor, from the excess of fluids and other residual materials.

Phase 5. – In the final, the cells are combined with a finalizing solution of „bio-ink” type and passed through a 3D printer, that shapes them under a fillet or medallion form, according to taste.

To mention that *biocellular preparations* (ex. Medallions of fish meat) may be cooked on direct heating, on steam or fried in oil, may be marinated in acid solutions for special preparations (poke, ceviche, kimchi, or even as sushi). The majority of those who have tasted the product (sensorial analyses) sustain that there is no difference between the biocellular product and the fish meat obtained from fish bread in water from nature or farm basins. An advantage for the fish biocellular products is that messmates are not stressed to debone.

Conclusions

It is „crystallized” a change of paradigm that will probably lead to a new World Order by the emergence of the alternative that, instead of the agro-zootechnical production on metabolic line based on the process of ontogenesis, to obtain natural food products on the basis of cellular multiplication in laboratory. The limitative factor is the resistance of the present mentality, strongly „rooted” in time, linked to psychological factors: the pleasure to eat, food taste, traditional products of local communities, customs and traditions and other. However, we are talking about complementarity and not about replacing the way food is produced, in order to ensure the necessary quantities of food in large urban agglomerations.

As a potential of biocellular food benefits we may have in view that, in comparison with the products of *conventional agriculture*, the *cellular agriculture* products have less effects upon environment, they are safer, purer and with a more consistent offer, aspects that are due to the fact that food is produced in modules in safety conditions, in controlled environment and space, including in cosmic space.

Biocellular natural food by *fortification* has the capacity to become „functional food” (i.e. biocellular food of meat type with less saturated fats and more no saturated fats, or with skin of different thicknesses; lactose-free milk; cholesterol-free eggs; supplements with vitamins or microelements useful for health and other).

Not only that bio cellular food is natural, but it is also clean, it does not contain drug residues or

hormones used to ensure the large productions from conventional agriculture and there are not made genetic manipulations at the cell level (for example of meat); at the same time there are not any more excessively used the agricultural surfaces to produce fodder, resulting advantages of economic and managerial order.

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IMPORTANCE OF WOOD BIOMASS IN ROMANIA

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Abstract: Romania is a country with a great potential in the field of renewable energy resources. The exploitation of biomass has a double benefit as an important source of renewable energy and the improvement of the environment and climate. Liquid biomass fuels are currently the least competitive due to low oil prices. Biofuels have a positive energy balance, although they vary from one category to another. Biomass is the vegetal component of nature. As a form of storing the sun energy in chemical form, biomass is one of the most popular and universal resources on Earth. It provides not only food, but also energy, construction materials, medicines and chemicals. Biomass is used for energetic purposes from the monument of human discovery of fire. Today biomass fuel can be used for different purposes, from heating rooms to producing electricity and car fuels. Biomass can be used in burners and ovens for house heating. Wood and other biomass resources represent a significant and ecological resource through the effects it produces.

Keywords: wood, calorimetric bomb, calorific value, energy efficiency

1. Introduction

Wood biomass comes from the wood that resulted from the cutting of tree crowns, but also from the quantities of wood to be processed. Basically, logging starts with cutting wood from the forest, cutting the branches and removing the roots. After that, the transport and storage operation is carried out within the processing companies. Here realized the sorting and classification by quality of the wood. Bark isn't good for the production of fermentable sugars, due to the high content of extractable substances and aromatic compounds [2, 8].

Briquettes and pellets are produced from wood waste such as chipping, sawdust, or agricultural waste. The quality the briquettes depend on the compressive strength and their density. They have a higher calorific value as they are more compressed. The briquettes are the most advantageous forms of heating of the houses. They are easily transported and stored. Briquettes according to our research, are considered solid and environmentally friendly fuels, as a source of heating.

The ecological materials that are often used on the energy market are the wood sawdust briquettes. In the last period of time the briquettes of vegetable have gained a special advantage.

The pellets are obtained by mechanical pressing of the wood material, results in smaller products.

Pellets are solid fuels with a low moisture content (max.12%). These are obtained from sawdust, wood chips, wood dust. The energy capacity of the pellets is 19700 kJ/kg (3250 kWh), at a moisture content of 0 %. Waste is classified by how it is used reusable waste, recycled waste, storage waste [1, 3, 9].

From the point of view of provenance, waste is classified as waste from the wood processing industry, domestic consumers and agricultural processing. In the structure of municipal waste in Romania, the largest share (81% have household waste). Street waste and construction waste have a share of 10 % and 9 % respectively.

In 2015, the amount of municipal waste collected through the mayors was 7.37 million tons. Today it is observed that biomass is constantly growing. On the territory of Romania, fuels can be obtained as well as bioethanol, vegetable oils, biodiesel, biogas, biomethanol and hydrogen. Vegetable plants from which these fuels can be obtained are: beat sugar, sugar sorghum, straw.

Agricultural plants are used to produce bioenergy from plants and could help reduce emissions of volatile substances.

Wood crops are differentiated by the following four factors: the amount of solar energy, the amount of energy intercepted by biomass, efficiency of photosynthetic conversion into energy, loss of biomass by exploitation.

In the European Union for 2011, 426.7 million m³ of round wood was cut and taking into account the fact that the waste resulting from logging is 10% of the material exploited, it follows that the total production of round wood resulted in a quantity of 42675.15 thousand m³ of waste [4, 7].

In 2004, in Romania 11000000 m³ / year of wood is exploited. In Romania at the level of 2010, the amount of wood material resulting from wood processing and from agricultural crops produces electricity of 671 GWh and 755 TJ is used for heat production. The total production of biomass resources is presented as follows:

- lucerne - 7846000 tons;
- corn – 7777600 tons;
- wheat- 5364014 tons;
- fodder plants- 4678167 tons;
- potatoes-3742300 tons;
- clover– 2704367 tons;
- vegetable- 1244867 tons;

- fire wood and charcoal- 3152600 tons;
- wood residues 243500 tons.

The energy potential of the biomass resulting from the use of vegetable waste products as fuel is evaluated at 7594 thousand toe/year and is composed of: residues from debarking and firewood 1175 thousand toe/year, wood waste and other wood 487 thousand toe/year, agricultural waste resulting from the production, maize stalks, vegetable 4799 thousand toe/year, urban waste and household waste 545 thousand toe/year [5, 6, 19].

2. Materials and method

According to research carried out at EU level there are a number of regulations on classification, determining calorific value combustible wood and product descriptions (DIN 51900-1, SR EN 1496-1). Determination of calorific wood is almost similar to that of coal [11, 16-18].

The installation used to determine the calorific value of wood biomass combustion was explosive XRY-1C type, produced by Schanghai Geological Instrument of China (fig.1).

Fig. 1. Calorimetric bomb

The process for determining the calorific value of the wood refers primarily to the preparation of raw materials and installation, and the determination itself and finally to final output [12, 20]. This sample is placed in a porcelain crucible and placed in a laboratory oven in order

to dry a temperature of 103°C. The determining process of calorific power of the wood is referring mainly to the preparation of the raw material, then to the actual determination and then to the obtaining of the fuel result. The preparation of the wood material for the testing

purpose consists in sampling a small part of 0.6-0.8 grams from the whole material, sample weight with an accuracy of 0.0002 grams. Preparing the installation for the test refers to checking the water quantity in the calorimeter [10, 13]. The testing sample 1 is tied to the cotton thread 2 and is placed in the bomb melting pot 3. The testing sample is tied to the spiral nichelina thread 4 and cotton thread, after which the protection lid is appropriately positioned 5. The

melting pot is tied to the calorimetric bomb lid 6 by two electrodes 7 and 8, which continue with the electric wires for coupling the calorimetric bomb 9 and 10. By screwing the bomb lid, the bomb 11 is coupled through the nozzle 12 to the oxygen tank 13, introducing 30 atmospheres.

The description of the process to assess the caloric power is presented in fig.2 [12, 15].

Fig. 2. Description of the process to assess the caloric power

For the *Carpinus Betulus*, at $U = 0\%$, $m = 0.6500$ g, higher caloric power = 18741 kJ/kg, lower caloric power = 18268 kJ/kg, at $U = 10\%$, $m = 0.9620$ g, higher caloric power = 16748 kJ/kg, lower caloric power = 16558 kJ/kg, energy efficiency = 98 %, at $U = 20\%$, $m = 0.9980$ g, higher caloric power = 14992 kJ/kg, lower

caloric power = 14613 kJ/kg, energy efficiency = 95 %, at $U = 50\%$, $m = 1.4040$ g, higher caloric power = 9724 kJ/kg, lower caloric power = 8776 kJ/kg, energy efficiency = 71%.

The variation of the energy efficiency for the *Carpinus Betulus* is shown in fig.3.

Fig. 3. The variation of the energy density for the *Carpinus Betulus*

Conclusions

The briquettes don't use the production of solid wood, only the residues after the exploitation of the trees and the wood processing; The briquettes protect the environment; Wood pellets are fuels with low carbon dioxide emissions;

The energy efficiency decrease with increase the moisture content of the samples; The optimum percentage of combustion is between the values of 10-20% moisture content of solid fuel material.

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NATURAL HONEY MARKET: EU28 AND BRICS COMPETITIVENESS EVIDENCES REGARDING MOUNTAIN NATURAL HONEY

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Abstract: The paper presents natural honey market conjuncture, accentuating the contribution of EU28 (European Union 28) and BRICS countries (Brazil, Russian Federation, India, China and South Africa) to the world market competitiveness. The presented countries hold more than a half of natural honey world production, being considered major players of the global market. Some of them are emergent countries and occupy an increasingly better place in the current structure of world trade. In the current pandemic crisis, the market of natural honey does not decline in trade value, quantity and some related indices, but increases. The analyzed indices regarding natural honey and countries competitiveness are Export Value, Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) for Agricultural Raw Materials (covering natural honey), Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI), Export Market Penetration (EMP). The paper presents evidences regarding mountain natural honey - manna honey, conifer honey and mountain multiflora honey, and how natural honey market is influenced by the indices presented above.

Keywords: natural honey, world honey conjuncture, mountain area, EU28 and BRICS competitiveness trade indices.

1. Introduction

World conjuncture of the natural honey commodity must be analyzed through relevant indices which influence this market on worldwide level. In this paper it has been chosen the indices share of Export in total world, Export Market Penetration (EMP), Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) for Agricultural Raw Materials (which cover the natural honey commodity) and Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI). Natural honey (NH) is a raw commodity which does not represent a high risking product for human health, being the main reason of trade linearity or rising in the current pandemic crisis. In general, world trade has decline in value and volume from the beginning of the COVID19 pandemic. Still, some of the products does not reduced in trade value and volume because are marketed in crude form and, consequently, does not affect the human health as much as processed food.

There are some other raw products which increase in trade value and volume, as oils, vegetables, fruits, and so on. But, the lowest degree of risk for human health is represented by natural honey, which does not expire and has a low degree of infection. In these respect, natural

honey could be considered the most important bioindicator of current emerging agricultural sector.

The paper presents the main natural honey world player, together with some relevant indices for the mentioned country associations (EU28 and BRICS), like Export Value, Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) for Agricultural Raw Materials group products, Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI), Export Market Penetration (EMP).

Export Value is the indicator that show the total value of a country export, and is reflecting the emergence of an industry into a country.

According to Word Bank (2020), Export Market Penetration (EMP) is calculated as the number of countries to which the reporter exports a particular product divided by the number of countries that report importing the product that year.

Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) or Balassa index compares a country's advantage for a product / raw material / economic good and is calculated as follows (World Bank, 2020; Covaci B., 2020):

$$RCA_{cp} = \frac{E_{cp} / \sum_{p \in P} E_{cp}}{\sum_{c' \in C} E_{c'p} / \sum_{c' \in C, p \in P} E_{c'p}}$$

where E represent Exports;

c, c' – Country index;

C – Set of countries;

p, p' –Commodity index and – Set of commodities.

The indicator of RCA compares for any industry its share in the total export of goods with the share held in the total import. The calculation of the indicator in the case of an industry takes into account, on the one hand on the one hand, the export of domestic production and, on the other hand, the competing imports domestic production (and not the import of intermediate goods for industrial production respectively). High values of the indicator reveal a comparative advantage for that industry. (Croitoru et al, 2001). For Agricultural Raw Materials the RCA is calculated taking into consideration products from agricultural field.

The indicator of the concentration of foreign trade (HHI) is obtained by determining the share of trade of a product or a group of products in the total trade. The relation used is:

$$I_x = \sum \left(\frac{x_i}{X} \right)^2$$

where: i is the number of products or group of products;

xi represents the exports of that product;

X represents the total export. (Covaci, 2016)

2. Methods and data

World bank data shows that EU28 and BRICS countries have an important share in total world trade. EMP for EU28 and BRICS countries present a table for 2018 as follow Brazil 12,62, Russian Federation 11,51, India 27,15, China 47,41, South Africa 12,13, Austria 18,64, Belgium 23,95, Bulgaria 10,09, Croatia 6,61, Cyprus 3,33, Czech Republic 17,00, Denmark 16,61, Estonia 6,52, Finland 11,36, France 32,49, Germany 39,82, Greece 9,54, Hungary 12,91, Ireland 9,27, Italy 35,61, Latvia 6,25, Lithuania 8,65, Luxembourg 5,90, Malta 2,99, Netherlands 27,07, Poland 20,73, Portugal 13,86, Romania 11,20, Slovakia 10,26, Slovenia 10,21, Spain 28,02, Sweden 17,29, United Kingdom 33,13.

RCA for 2017 present an important trend for EU28 and BRICS countries – showing the emergence of these country groups, as follow: Brazil 3,64, Russian Federation 1,92, India 0,86, China 11,82, South Africa 0,12, Austria 0,86, Belgium 0,7, Bulgaria 0,72, Croatia 3,5, Cyprus 0,94, Czech Republic 0,8, Denmark 2,08, Estonia 5,33, Finland 5,57, France 0,67, Germany 0,54

Greece 1,62, Hungary 0,38, Ireland 0,25, Italy 0,46, Latvia 8,53, Lithuania 1,81, Luxembourg 1,11, Malta 0,19, Netherlands 1,98, Poland 0,83, Portugal 2,05, Romania 0,96, Slovakia 0,64, Slovenia 1,23, Spain 0,77, Sweden 3,12, United Kingdom 0,43.

HHI index for 2018 present the world top for EU28 and BRICS countries as follow: Brazil 0,11, Russian Federation 0,04, India 0,05, China 0,06, South Africa 0,07, Austria 0,10, Belgium 0,07, Bulgaria 0,05, Croatia 0,06, Cyprus 0,04, Czech Republic 0,11, Denmark 0,06, Estonia 0,06, Finland 0,05, France 0,05, Germany 0,04, Greece 0,03, Hungary 0,09, Ireland 0,12, Italy 0,04, Latvia 0,05, Lithuania 0,04, Luxembourg 0,09, Malta 0,04, Netherlands 0,09, Poland 0,09, Portugal 0,08, Romania 0,08, Slovakia 0,07, Slovenia 0,07, Spain 0,06, Sweden 0,04, United Kingdom 0,05.

Regarding natural honey, these country groups have a share of 55,22% in total export. Brazil hold 3,41% in total natural honey market (world raking in natural honey top WR 9), Russian Federation 0,28% (WR 39), India 5,07% (WR 6), China 11,82% (WR 1), South Africa 0,12% (WR 49), Austria 0,86% (WR 25), Belgium 3,19% (WR 10), Bulgaria 2,07% (WR 16), Croatia 0,10% (WR 54), Cyprus insignificant (WR 86), Czech Republic 0,25 % (WR 40), Denmark 0,80% (WR 28), Estonia 0,02% (WR 69), Finland insignificant (WR 92), France 1,51% (WR 18), Germany 6,61% (WR 4), Greece 0,74% (29), Hungary 4,25% (WR 8), Ireland 0,33% (WR 37), Italy 1,37% (WR 20), Latvia 0,04 % (WR 63), Lithuania 0,25% (WR 40), Luxembourg insignificant (WR 84), Malta insignificant (WR 116), Netherlands 0,98% (WR 24), Poland 2,17% (WR 14), Portugal 0,63% (WR 31), Romania 2,20% (13), Slovakia 0,04% (WR 62), Slovenia 0,12% (WR 51), Spain 4,44% (WR 75), Sweden 0,07% (WR 55), United Kingdom 1,50% (WR 19).

Natural honey is different from region to region, from space to space. One of the complex natural honey is mountain honey. "Not all honey are made equal... There are 300 known types of honey, produced by over 20,000 honey bee species, that vary in flavor, color, and health effects. For this reason, honey type and composition vary with geography, and angiosperm and honey bee species distribution." (Otero & Bernolo, 2020)

Methods used in the paper are qualitative and quantitative. Qualitative, it has been studied many scientific and professional papers and

synthesized the important idea. Quantitative, the author took and processed data from World Bank, World Integrated Trade Solution and International Trade Centre websites.

3. Results

Analyzed trade indices show that EU28 and BRICS countries tend to become more powerful in world trade, especially in exports. (figure 1 and 2).

Fig. 1. EU28 trade market competitiveness – general, agricultural raw materials and natural honey indices

Fig. 2. BRICS trade market competitiveness – general, agricultural raw materials and natural honey indices

Emergent countries as China, India, Poland grew up in market penetration on worldwide trade, while others, Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Spain and United Kingdom straighten their position in exports. Other countries as Denmark, Czech Republic and Hungary tend to occupy more in export market penetration in 2018.

In the last years, important countries from EU28 and BRICS, as Brazil, China, Croatia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Greece, Latvia, Portugal, and Sweden increased their comparative advantage for agricultural raw materials on worldwide. Others like Russian Federation, South Africa, Austria, Denmark, Greece, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands and Slovenia becomes emergent countries in RCA for agricultural raw materials. (figure 1 and 2)

As seen, Brazil, Austria, Czech Republic and Ireland present a good HHI, meaning that their products become more competitive in 2018. But other countries grew up in HHI world sharing, namely South Africa, Belgium, Hungary, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia. (figure 1 and 2)

Regarding natural honey, EU28 and BRICS countries are among the top 75% in the world ranking, the majority are in the first half of the rankings, and countries with relevant RCA between the first 6%. Some of the top leaders of the natural honey exports from EU28 and BRICS countries are Brazil, India, China, Belgium, Germany, Hungary, and Spain. Other countries become in the last years more competitive on the natural honey market, respectively France, Italy, Poland, Romania and United Kingdom. Romania is between the first 8% in the world ranking top. (figure 1 and 2)

Mountain natural honey is found in few forms such as manna honey, conifer honey and mountain multiflora honey. (Rey et. all, 2019). "Mountain honey is a hybrid grape tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) resulting from the cross of NC 4 grape × NC 6 grape... It has a compact indeterminate plant with short internodes conferred by the brachytic (br) gene and has dark red fruit with high total soluble solids." (Panthee & Randy, 2013)

In Romania mountain honey is the most appreciated type of honey, but not so consumed because is more expansive than others and insufficient promoted. In a major study realized in 2012, on 1449 persons, at the North-West region of Romania, the respondents answer that this type of honey is the most preferred, being impressed by it. As reminded, the problem with

this honey is the promotion, being insufficient advertised. (Pocol, 2012)

Mountain honey is preferred because has more benefits on health than others, like antiseptic, antimicrobial, anti-diabetic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, wound healing, regulatory of blood pressure and cardiovascular function, anti-cancer. The most common known bioactive components of honey are probiotics, prebiotics, quercetin, hesperitin, luteolin, kaempferol, galangin, naringenin, isorhamnetin, bee defensin-1. (Otero & Bernolo, 2020)

Manna honey is the only assortment of honey that does not come totally from the nectar of flowers, its origin being credited from the sweet secretions of trees or the sweet excretion of aphids, small green insects. Thus, we can consider that manna honey can have either vegetable origin, result of plant secretion, or animal, taken from the excretion of aphids. Manna honey has the highest mineral content, being the highly prized, especially due to the fact that it can be consumed by people allergic to floral pollen. It is rightly considered a real mineral cocktail, the mineral content in manna honey being, for example, six times higher than in acacia honey. This variety of honey also contains antioxidants such as phenols or flavonoids. Also, there was a high content of bioactive components compared to other types of honey, the content of enzymes and antibiotics being much higher than honey from flower nectar. Manna honey has a special value for human consumption and due to the content of organic acids, bioflavonoids, vitamin C and B vitamins. Due to its high mineral content it is frequently recommended in the treatment of spasmophilia in adolescents, rickets in children and adolescents, in osteoporosis and joint disease in both adults and the elderly. (Terra Apis, 2020)

Conifer honey is a type of honey that bees produce by collecting sap from the leaves or branches of conifers such as fir, pine, spruce. Conifer honey is slightly more fragrant and can smell a slight smell of fir resin. Particularly important is the presence of over 30 species of endemic plants or declared monuments of nature, whose survival is not possible outside a network of protected areas. The coniferous forest is the largest terrestrial habitat in the world. Conifer honey could be one of the most quantitative and qualitative honey of the world. This type of honey is specific for antiseptic and respiratory disease. (Maxantifurti, 2020)

Mountain multiflora honey hints of fruits and berries in the distance and is made to over 850 meters above sea level. "Recent studies have shown how the biodiversity becomes richer in proportion to the mountain altitude, with an extraordinary increase in the number of flowers above 850 meters (with 80 different species in the spring and over 130 in the summer). Among the most common plants are many grasses, rock roses and mints, along with white clover, blackberry and other members of the rose family, poppies, sainfoin and bird's foot trefoil, while ivy and wild asparagus flower in the late summer." (Slow Food Foundation for Biodiversity, 2020)

Natural honey, if not properly stored, presents often problems regarding alteration. Spontaneous fermentation is the main form of honey alteration. The process is triggered by a wide range of yeasts, which can be associated with some bacteria capable of fermenting sugars. The main sources of pollution of bee products are the environment and the substances used by beekeepers for the treatment of bee diseases. The activity of bees is influenced by all elements of the environment (soil, vegetation, air and water). (Pohl, 2009). The yeasts influence is difficult to control perfectly, in consequence the honey production could be easily damaged if the entrepreneurs (producers and distributors) are not attentive to the entire biodiversity of the mentioned environment elements. In addition, S. Bogdanov (2006) points out that the danger of contamination of natural honey lies in a greater extent from beekeeping practices than from the environment. Beekeepers must take action to prevent contamination of bee products by opting for ecological alternatives in disease control, by using non-toxic natural substances instead of synthetic ones. The purity of bee products depends on the period of their collection, the type of plant composition and the location of the apiary location (Lebedev & Muratova, 2003). Lebedev & Muratova (2003) found that of all bee products, honey is a pure ecological product, propolis, pasture and pollen being more polluted with heavy metals (Eremia et al, 2016).

Conclusions

The paper shows that natural honey market is influenced by the world production and trade, and by related indices. In the article are presented the EU28 and BRICS because these country groups have more than a half of natural honey world market. The analyzed indices regarding

natural honey and countries competitiveness were Export Value, Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) for Agricultural Raw Materials (covering natural honey), Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI), Export Market Penetration (EMP).

Regarding world exports and export market penetration countries as China, India, Poland become emergently, while Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Spain and United Kingdom straighten production and exports position.

RCA for agricultural raw materials presents an interesting worldwide picture, showing that Brazil, China, Croatia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Greece, Latvia, Portugal, and Sweden straightened their comparative advantage. Instead, countries like Russian Federation, South Africa, Austria, Denmark, Greece, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands and Slovenia become emergently in worldwide comparative advantage.

The last presented index, HHI, show that some of the countries, as Brazil, Austria, Czech Republic and Ireland, become more competitive on worldwide production and trade market, while South Africa, Belgium, Hungary, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, becomes emergently.

The paper presents evidences regarding mountain natural honey - manna honey, conifer honey and mountain multiflora honey, and show that these types of natural honey are excellent for health and nutrition. Consequently, mountain honey must be more promoted and people have to be educated in the spirit of consuming this type of honey. The countries with high RCA for agricultural raw materials, HHI and EMP could access easily the world honey market. But the country with significant mountain area could have an important trade advantage because of the mountain honey production.

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DEMARCATIION AND PROTECTION OF *Pistacia atlantica* Desf. IN SETIFIAN STEPPE (NORTH- EAST OF ALGERIA)

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Abstract: Rare endemic and threatened with extinction, *Pistacia atlantica* Desf. is one of the heritage species of Algeria, it occupies a very important place from an ecological and socio-economic point of view. The Atlas pistachio tree is distinguished by very high resistance and known for its high plasticity and its adaptation to arid and semi - arid climates. In the region of Sétif *Pistacia atlantica* Desf. exists only in the semi-arid Setifian steppe, in djebel Boutaleb, djebel Youssef and djebel Zdim. Faced with its vulnerability, this species confined to a very restricted area, requires protection and sustainability of its development to ensure its sustainability within the Sétif region.

Keywords: *Pistacia atlantica* Desf, Endemism, Vulnerability, Valuation, Sustainability, Sétif.

1. Introduction

Having a very limited distribution area in Algeria, the Atlas pistachio tree (*Pistacia atlantica* Desf.) is an endemic species, present in semi-arid, arid and even Saharan regions. According to Ramade [1], endemism is a phenomenon by which a species or a taxonomic group is strictly subservient to a given biogeographical area, generally of limited surface, in which it has differentiated due to the existence of special ecological conditions specific to the area. The most characteristic of the Atlas of Algeria, this species constitutes very important populations both ecologically and biogeographically and with its inescapable interests and its multiple uses, continues to decline from year to year following climate impacts and especially anthropogenic.

It is important to note that in Algeria the Atlas pistachio tree is one of the unknown resources on the ecological and floristic level, there is no specific and exhaustive national inventory on the stands of *Pistacia atlantica* Desf. and their distribution areas. Most of the work carried out on this species has focused on histomorphological studies [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. Very rare are the phytoecological studies carried out in western Algeria and in the Sahara [8, 9]. We note that no study has been carried out on the phytoecology of the Atlas pistachio tree in eastern Algeria.

The Atlas pistachio tree generally develops in a sparse and isolated form, it is known among the species which have a resistance to natural phenomena in steppe and arid areas, subject to edapho-climatic constraints on the one hand and anthropogenic on the other hand, it supports strong winds and long periods of drought amplified by increasing pressure from man and his herds.

This ecological plasticity gives it a very important place from the point of view of floristic study and delimitation of its stands in interaction with their habitats, the aim of which is their protection and sustainable development. Currently we are witnessing an overexploitation of *Pistacia atlantica* Desf products in the steppe region of the Hautes Plains Sétifiennes.

The growing problem facing the region is the gradual disappearance of this species, a non-renewable resource, reported as rare endemic to protect [10].

Thus our objectives aim at a better knowledge on the populations of *Pistacia atlantica* and on their areas of distribution by fighting against the factors of degradation due to the abusive anthropic activities.

This is necessary to better manage the threats which weigh on this species and to establish an adequate management plan to support its balanced and sustainable development in the Sétif region.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Studied area

Located in the southern part of the wilaya of Sétif, this sector includes several djebels including djebel Youssef, djebel Zdimm and djebel Boutaleb which constitute the southern limit (fig.1), beyond, towards the south is the depression of Hodna, which constitutes a Saharan enclave within the high steppe plains. These three massifs are located in the southern part of the high Plains of Setif, where the steppe influence is quite marked [10].

Djebel Youssef stretches from east to west over ten km between coordinates $36^{\circ} 01'21.5''$ North and $5^{\circ} 24'50.7''$ East. It rises to 1442 m with foothills around 910 m altitude.

Djebel Zdimm is located about twenty km west of djebel Youssef between $36^{\circ} 01'30.5''$ North

and $5^{\circ} 10'06.6''$ East. It rises to an altitude of 1258 m and foothills of 900 m.

These two steep massifs with their steep slopes are in contact with two structural groups, the platform of the Setifian tell to the north and the salt depressions (chotts and sebkha) to the south.

Djebel Boutaleb constitutes an important and well individualized link in the eastern part of the chain of the Hodna mountains between the geographical coordinates of $35^{\circ} 41'14.7''$ North and $5^{\circ} 15'50.4''$ East. It is located between the high Sétifian plains to the north and the Hodna basin to the south .

Djebel Boutaleb has relatively high altitudes, varying between 980 m and 1886 m.

The south of Setif, has essentially limestone soils with most often hard limestone accumulations near the surface [11]. These soils generally have a thin, skeletal surface horizon poor in organic matter.

Fig.1. Location of study sites. Site 1: Djebel Zdimm; Site 2: djebel Youssef; Site 3: djebel Boutaleb

The soils of djebel Youssef are shallow stony of two types : bedded black dolomites with intercalation of marly limestones at the base and limestones at the top. While djebel Zdimm shows a succession of coarse limestone and greasy limestone with a marl-limestone bedrock and compact limestones at the top The soils of djebel Boutaleb are calcimagnesian brown limestone and brown calcic soils, these brunified soils are rich in fine silicate elements [12].

The hydrographic network of the delimited sector is organized in its entirety in an endorheic

system. The various wadis correspond to temporary watercourses with a main flow in the form of floods. They drain the massifs towards the permanent wadis, for the northern slopes and towards the closed depressions for the southern slopes. The water regime is very variable depending on the rainfall: rainy years and others dry.

From a biogeographical point of view, the site belongs to the North African steppe domain [13,14], to the highlands sector and sub-sector of the Constantine highlands [15], (Quézel & Santa,

1962-1963). The study area is located in a semi-arid bioclimate below cool winter, with average precipitation estimated at 440.60 mm / year and thermal amplitudes varying between 1.94°C and 37.7°C with a relatively long dry season of 5½ months. Belonging to the semi-arid Meso-Mediterranean vegetation stage [10]. The flora of this ecosystem is remarkable, notably with low matorrals and wooded and chamaephytic steppes [16,17].

2.2. Methodology

Our investigations in the south of Sétif, purely phytocological, are aimed at the search for endemic taxa and the delimitation of their distribution areas for their protection. Our choice is made on the species *Pistacia atlantica* Desf, an endemic tree that has not benefited from a typical ecological study in the Sétif region. This species is reported only in the southern part of the high Sétifian plains in the Boutaleb massif (Sedjar, 2012) and in the steppe region, on djebel Zdimm and djebel Youssef [17].

In addition to these studies and aimed at researching the Atlas pistachio tree, our approach

was to carry out field trips by sweeping all sides of the mountain ranges in the south of Sétif using floristic surveys and the use of GPS. Thus we have had recourse to the topographical maps and flora [15, 18,19]. The delimited sector was subdivided into three distinct sites according to physiographic and floristic criteria. The study period spans 4 years from 2016 to 2019.

3. Results

One of the highlights of the demarcated area is its individualization by stands of *Pistacia atlantica* Desf which constitute the last shrub landscape of the semi-arid Setifien steppe and a buttress against desertification. This endemic species is distributed in a rather small geographical area and found nowhere else in the region of Sétif. It rubs shoulders with many thermo-xerophytic steppe species and coincides with the Meso and thermo-Mediterranean vegetation stage. According to ecological macro-criteria, we can distinguish three localities of the Atlas pistachio (fig.2).

Fig. 2. Range of the Atlas pistachio tree in the south of Setif

Site 1- djebel Zdimm: on its southern flank and particularly in the wooded steppe. The Atlas pistachio tree is scattered in islets of 3 to 7 feet on the reliefs between 1100 and 1200 m of altitude between the thermophilic phanerophytes including *Juniperus phoenicea* L., *Zizyphus lotus* (L.) Desf., *Deverra scoparia* Cosson & Durieu, *Pinus halepensis* Mill. and *Stipa tenacissima* L. This site is distinguished by the presence of a

single and isolated individual of the Atlas pistachio tree (*Betouma maabouda*) at an altitude of 1240m on a vertical cliff. This old and large tree is well preserved by the local population and marabouts, it represents the sacred and oldest tree in this steppe. A similar phenomenon reported Morocco [20], in the eastern region of Morocco where the preservation of the pistachio tree in this area, whose approximate age is approaching

a century, essentially comes down to the belief of the inhabitants.

On the other hand, on the northern slope of this massif, in the chaméphytic steppe, between 1004 and 1180m of altitude, a dozen feet of *Pistacia atlantica* Desf. Are found in a very degraded state accompanied most often by thermo-xerophyte species including *Artemisia herba-alba* Asso, *Astragalus armatus* Willd., *Launaea arborescens* (Batt.)M., *Asparagus albus* L., *Rhamnus lycioides* L., *Asparagus acutifolius* L., *Asparagus stipularis* Forssk., these taxa of rock gardens and pastures, are representative of the most anthropized areas by Djebel Zdimm [10].

Site 2 - djebel Youssef : within the summit formations of this massif, 11 small populations of Atlas pistachio were observed of 4 to 11 individuals on the North and North-West slope with several trees and shrubs thermophiles based on *Crataegus azarolus* L., *Juniperus oxycedrus* L., *Phillyrea angustifolia* L., *Olea europea* L., *Calicotome spinosa* (L.) Link, *Prunus prostrata* Labill., *Quercus rotundifolia* L., *Pinus halepensis* Mill. and *Rhamnus alaternus* L. This formation degraded occupies altitudes between 1270 and 1400m.

Site 3- djebel Boutaleb: on the northern slope of between 1050 and 1300 m is structured by a mixed facies of wooded steppes where the feet of

Pistacia atlantica Desf. are well protected by *Zizyphus lotus* L. and accompanied by *Phillyrea angustifolia* L., *Juniperus phoenicea* L., *Pinus halepensis* Mill. and *Juniperus oxycedrus* L. and *Globularia alypum* L. This site located in the extreme south of the Sétif region, it represents the last pistachio trees in the Atlas of the Setifian region with a population of 58 individuals observed covering an area of approximately 100 m².

4. Discussions

4.1. New range of *Pistacia atlantica* Desf.

According to our investigations in the Sétif region, the Atlas pistachio tree is found only in the south of Sétif. It currently forms degraded stands, rather isolated individuals between steppe vegetation that may be partly linked to the sporadic presence of microhabitats under anthropogenic pressure. This species is well acclimatized in the semi-arid Setifian steppes in the thermo and meso-Mediterranean vegetation stage [17]. On djebel Zdimm, it grows on cliffs at an altitude of 1200 m as well as in the wooded steppe (fig.3). On djebel Youssef and djebel Boutaleb, the Atlas pistachio tree stands out at high altitudes between 1300 and 1400 m.

Fig.3. *Pistacia atlantica* Desf. growing on the northern slope of djebel Youssef (September 2018)

4.2. Habitat and acclimatization

The Atlas pistachio tree is reported as the most original and remarkable species in North Africa. It is a tree par excellence of the dayas of the southern foothills of the Saharan Atlas, its extreme limit is in the heart of the Hoggar where it exists in relic state [2].

It is mainly found in the transition zone between the steppe and the Tell, especially in the western region of Algeria. From East to West it is found in M'Sila, Djelfa, Tlemcen, Saida, Tiaret, Naama, Laghouat, El Bayad, Béchar and

Ghardaia. It is also recorded at the southern limit of Algeria at the level of Hoggar [8]. It is one of the rare tree species still present in semi-arid and arid regions, and even in the Saharan region. This exceptional plasticity vis-à-vis atmospheric drought could be its main character, but it is no less indifferent to the nature of the soil and it can occupy the most extreme situations in its botanical area [2].

The floristic procession of *Pistacia atlantica* Desf is consistent with the bioclimate and its habitat, it is most often associated with *Zizyphus*

lotus, *Juniperus phoenicea*, *Pinus halepensis* and many steppe chaméphytes. This intimate association gives it good protection against winds and entropic action, particularly grazing [10, 21, 22, 20, 24].

The pistachio trees of the Atlas of the High Plains of Setif have a large thermal amplitude and are subject to drastic variations in periods of drought going to more than 5 dry months and strong anthropozoic pressure [17].

4.3. Vulnerability status and protection

As the most original and remarkable species of North Africa, the Atlas Pistachio is one of the rare tree species still present in the semi - arid and arid regions of Algeria [25]. Most of the Atlas pistachio range is in western Algeria. It is a heritage species of global interest.

According to decree n ° 93-285 corresponding to November 23, 1993, *Pistacia atlantica* Desf. is declared in the list establishing the non-cultivated plant species protected throughout the Algerian territory.

Pistacia atlantica Desf. is a species of the future for western Algeria, its resistance to all ecological hazards gives it a special status compared to species from southern Algeria [22]. Depending on the level of exploitation, the decline in the overall size of this species is estimated at 25% over the next 100 years [26].

In the steppe ecosystems of Setif, the Atlas pistachio tree is undergoing severe degradation due to climatic deterioration and strong anthropization. This situation is detrimental to plant resources and the loss of an endemic taxon reported for the first time in the south of Sétif. This makes it possible to attribute to this species the status of rarity in eastern Algeria.

Due to its alarming level of vulnerability, its sustainability and its ecological and socioeconomic interest in the Sétifienne region, it is recommended to establish an emergency intervention plan whose main conservation strategies aim to delimit the protected areas of this species by the creation of plant belts using the thorny and non-palatable or hardly palatable accompanying species originating from these stations such as *Ziziphus lotus* (L.), *Launaea arborescens* (Batt.) M, *Rhus tripartita* (Ucria) Grande, *Thymelaea microphylla* Coss and Dur. *Deverra scoparia* Cosson & Durieu.

Thus a mastery of the knowledge of *Pistacia atlantica* Desf. on its biology and dynamics will allow its extension and maintenance in the future.

The natural conservation of the Atlas pistachio tree is a challenge to be taken up in the Sétif region, given its high vulnerability combined with human pressure and climatic hazards.

Conclusions

The Atlas pistachio tree is a tree well adapted to semi-arid and arid climates. Reported for the first time in the Sétif region, this species is in a precarious and alarming situation because of its extensive degradation. In the absence of a precise delimitation of its distribution area in Algeria, this work allows us to understand to what extent the data on the Algerian Atlas pistachio may still be incomplete and it is necessary that research on *Pistacia atlantica* Desf. should broaden and deepen the spectrum of territorial prospecting surveys of the eastern steppes.

Classified as rare endemic and threatened with extinction in the near future, the Atlas pistachio tree, which occupies a very restricted distribution area in the Sétif region, must urgently receive protection status and multidisciplinary efforts must be deployed. quickly to conserve, support and rehabilitate it in these fragile and vulnerable steppe ecosystems.

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FOOD SAFETY IN PASTEURIZATION OF LIQUID FOOD - BASIC ELEMENTS FOR MOUNTAIN FARMERS

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Abstract: Pasteurization is a heat treatment aimed at reducing the number of harmful microorganisms to a level at which they do not constitute a significant health hazard. There are however many reasons why, in practice pasteurized products may present a microbiological health hazard. Due to the pasteurizer equipment process design, the operation and control or inspection and maintenance of the pasteurizer there are a risk of unpasteurized or re-contaminated product may reach the consumer. This paper explain some technical issues that should be take in consideration in order to achieve a high level of food safety.

Keywords: food safety, diary, mountain farms

1. Introduction

Pasteurization is a heat treatment process applied to a product with the aim of avoiding a public health hazard arising from vegetative pathogenic microorganisms associated with milk and other low acid products. The pasteurization temperature and the lower temperature limits that define when to divert product or stop the pasteurization must be based on legal requirements or discussed with health authorities. For pasteurizing of milk a temperature and time combination of 72°C and 16 to 30 seconds holding time is widely recognized in Europe. This temperature and time combination is sufficient to destroy the pathogenic microorganism in the milk. Other products might require other conditions. For pasteurization to result in a microbiologically safe product, it is necessary that:

- the correct pasteurization conditions are maintained during the entire period of operation;
- unacceptable re-contamination of pasteurized product is prevented [16, 17].

To maintain the correct pasteurization conditions, the temperature measuring-equipment must be sufficiently accurate and reliable. The same applies to the equipment that ensures that the treatment time is correct; the flow of product must not exceed a value that will

lead to the product having too short a residence time of product in the holding section of the pasteurizer. Similarly, the volume of the holding section should not be allowed to decrease unacceptably as a result of fouling. To prevent re-contamination, the equipment downstream from the heating section of the pasteurizer must be pre-pasteurized before pasteurization of the product is started [2, 3, 5].

The equipment must be cleanable, preferably cleanable in-place. The second important purpose of pasteurization is the keeping quality aspect. Pasteurization can deactivate enzymes and reduce the number of spoilage bacteria in order to maintain the quality of the pasteurized product over the intended shelf life. A pasteurization process is applied to ensure a specified shelf life to various kind of food that must be stored under refrigerated conditions. In high-acid products such as many fruit juices (with a pH below 4.5), harmful spore forming bacteria cannot multiply.

Therefore, if such a product is treated at a temperature that inactivates all relevant vegetative microbes and the product is aseptically packed, the product may be stored at ambient temperature and for a very long time (depending on quality deterioration rather than microbiological safety) [15]. Aseptically packed in this case means that the product contact side of the packing material is decontaminated to inactivate all relevant microbes and that the

sealed packs are impervious to microbes (“bacteria-tight”). In this case, the equipment downstream from the heating section must be impervious to bacteria as well. The specification of the correct pasteurization temperature and time combination is fully the responsibility of the food manufacturer.

2. Pasteurizer process design

The configuration of the pasteurizer is very important. The design must ensure that every particle of product receives the correct pasteurization temperature and time, as well as an overpressure on the pasteurized side to minimize the risk of re-contamination.

The system should also be designed to handle any deviations to these critical parameters in a safe way. The equipment must be of hygienic design and designed and operated in a way to prevent re-contamination by pathogenic microbes [8, 11].

The design of the pasteurizer must be such that the risk of product being re-infected by non-pasteurized product in dead legs (pipes leading to valves, pressure gauges, temperature probes, etc.) or by other equipment in the line is prevented. A continuous pasteurizer consists of a heating section, a holding section and in most cases a heat regeneration and/or a cooling section.

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The equipment must be of hygienic design and designed and operated in a way to prevent re-contamination by pathogenic microbes [1, 10]. The design of the pasteurizer must be such that the risk of product being re-infected by non-pasteurized product in dead legs (pipes leading to valves, pressure gauges, temperature probes, etc.) or by other equipment in the line is prevented. A continuous pasteurizer consists of a heating section, a holding section and in most cases a heat regeneration and/or a cooling section.

2.1 Holding section

The function of the holding section is to ensure that each element of fluid entering it receives a minimum desired heat treatment e.g. remains at the pasteurization temperature for the required

holding time to assure the destruction of the pathogenic microorganisms. The residence time in the holding tube is affected by the geometry and the flow rate. Higher volumetric flow rates will decrease the residence time. The residence time must not decrease to below a certain minimum value; this may depend on legal requirements and should be confirmed by health authorities.

The flow pattern must be taken into account very carefully (the ratio of average velocity to maximum velocity in a holding tube varies between 0.5 in a laminar flow which means a Reynolds number below Re 2.300 to 0.82 in fully turbulent flow).

FDA use Re 4.000 as a limit. Turbulent flow is the preferred option but cannot always be achieved for viscous products. For laminar flow the holding tube may need to be up to twice the length calculated on the basis of the average holding time in order to achieve the minimum residence time. Specification of the correct residence time is the responsibility of the food manufacturer.

To ensure that the minimum residence time is maintained, it is essential that, during pasteurization of a certain product:

- The flow rate must not increase above the design flow rate.
- Fouling over the specified production time should be taken into account and the holding tube designed accordingly.
- Holding tubes should be of a design where air pockets are not present thus reducing the effective holding time. The product flow should be from the bottom to the top.
- The pressure in the system should be high enough to avoid boiling.

2.2 Temperature

The pasteurization temperature and lower temperature limit to determine when to transfer products or stop pasteurization must be based on legal requirements or discussed with health authorities. The correct temperature is entirely the responsibility of the food manufacturer. If you choose a set point, you must consider the accuracy of the temperature measurement system [2, 4].

Furthermore, it must be possible to verify the temperature probes versus accredited references. It is recommended to use two temperature probes for temperature control and temperature recording.

The probe for the automatic temperature control is ideally positioned close to the heater outlet to achieve a short response time. The probe for the recorder has to be positioned at the end of the holding tube upstream of the diversion valve.

Products with a high viscosity often have a non-turbulent flow. In this case, especially at heater outlets the temperature distribution across the cross section may not be even.

To achieve better temperature uniformity a static mixer may be installed before the probe. Independent of the chosen solution the most important criteria to meet is the measurement of the lowest temperature in the product [9, 13].

3. Process operation

3.1 Disinfection of equipment by hot water

To disinfect the equipment downstream from the heating section of the pasteurizer, if a cooling section is present it is switched off and water is circulated until the temperature at the very end of the process line has reached the correct temperature. Circulation is continued for the sufficient time to reach the desired level of inactivation of relevant microorganisms present on the product contact surfaces. If the temperature at the end of the process line becomes too low during circulation, the phase should be re-started.

The disinfection step is a must before production can take place. If disinfection is done by means of hot water, the temperature should be as a minimum, the subsequent pasteurization temperature for the required contact time, typically 20 minutes or more.

3.2 Start-up of product pasteurization

After successfully completing the disinfection, if there is a cooling circuit, it must be turned on. Once all the temperatures in the entire system are correct, the water in the balance tank can be replaced with the product to be pasteurized.

It is important to realize that as the product viscosity increases, the heat transfer from water to product may reduce the heat transfer rate.

The equipment manufacturer is responsible for ensuring that the design can adapt to changes in the heat transfer rate and that the temperature of the heating medium is high enough to achieve the required heat transfer rate at any time [6, 7].

The liquid level control system should ensure that there is always a minimum liquid level in the balance tank to prevent air from being sucked into the system.

3.3 Product pasteurization (production)

In order to maintain correct pasteurization conditions, temperature measurement equipment must be sufficiently accurate and reliable. The same is true for equipment that ensures the correct treatment time. The flow rate of the product should not exceed the value that causes the product to stay too short in the storage area of the pasteurizer. Similarly, due to fouling, the volume of the holding part should not be allowed to decrease by an unacceptable amount, as this will also shorten the heat treatment time. When too much fouling occurs, the pasteurization process must be stopped.

3.4 Cleaning

Cleaning takes place at the end of production or after a process deviation and the main requirements are:

- All product contact surfaces must be clean at the end of the cleaning sequence. Failure to achieve this may compromise the disinfection step.

- Chemicals must be compatible with the materials of construction at the in-use temperatures and concentrations.

- After cleaning, the chemicals must be removed from the plant by means of adequate water rinses. An efficient clean is achieved by mechanical and chemical effects, together with an increase in temperature.

The main parameters governing the cleaning process are cleaning temperature, cleaning flow, detergent concentration and cleaning time. These are all closely related. The effectiveness of the cleaning needs to be validated at start-up of a pasteurization line: the correct conditions must be maintained and regularly monitored. To ensure that the diversion return line is cleaned, the diversion valve should be actuated alternatively during every cleaning step [12, 14].

Consequently, to ensure adequate cleaning, the total cleaning time may have to be increased. If the pasteurizer has been out of production for an extended time period, it might require a cleaning in place cycle to be undertaken before disinfection. It is the responsibility of the food manufacturer to secure that an efficient disinfection is not compromised due to microbial and/or other deposits forming layers on the internal surfaces. The valve arrangement and pipe system after the flow diversion valve and after the recirculation valve should be designed so all interior surfaces are self-draining. It is recommended to fully drain the equipment before

an extended time period of no production to prevent the growth of microbes and the increased risk of corrosion.

The need to drain the equipment depends on the specific conditions such as water quality, temperature, type of equipment and is the responsibility of the food manufacturer to decide.

Conclusions

In order to ensure the microbiological safety of a pasteurized product the following must be achieved:

1. The measuring and control equipment have to ensure that correct temperature and time are retained.
2. Unacceptable errors in key process variables must result in promptly automatic flow diversion or shutdown of the pasteurizer.
3. The production process must be stopped before the discharge becomes significant (and therefore would significantly reduce the retention volume and thus the retention time) or before the growth of thermophilic bacteria in the regenerative section becomes too great.
4. The process equipment downstream of the retention tube must have a hygienic design and therefore be cleanable, possibly for disinfection / sanitization and bacterial tightness.
5. An effective separation between pasteurized and non-pasteurized product should be ensured.
6. Means to prevent the risk of mixing pasteurized and non-pasteurized product must be implemented.

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